

Chapter 5

REALIZING A SUSTAINABLE WORLD FOR NATURE AND PEOPLE: TRANSFORMATIVE STRATEGIES, ACTIONS AND ROLES FOR ALL¹

COORDINATING LEAD AUTHORS:

Hannah Gosnell (United States of America),
Victoria Reyes-García (Spain), Yves Zinngrebe (Germany)

LEAD AUTHORS:

Rafael Almeida Magris (Brazil), Karina Benessaiah (Canada, Tunisia, Greece/Canada), Martha Bonilla-Moheno (Mexico), Rodwell Chandipo (Zambia), Joachim Claudet (France), Barbara Gemmill-Herren (Switzerland/United States of America), Bruce Goldstein (United States of America), Patrick Huntjens (Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Chinwe Ifejiika Speranza (Nigeria, Switzerland/Switzerland), Fumiko Nakao (Japan), Ram Pandit (Nepal/Australia, Japan), Laura M. Pereira (South Africa, Portugal/South Africa, Sweden), Kristina Raab (Canada, United States of America/Germany), Thais Soares (Brazil), Pablo Tittone (Argentina/France, Netherlands [Kingdom of the]).

FELLOWS:

Xiaona Guo (China), Koji Miwa (Japan).

CONTRIBUTING AUTHORS:

Khalid Aayoud (Morocco), Terezhiah Achieng (Kenya/United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Elsa Cardona Santos (Mexico), Josephine Chambers (United States of America/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Jude Currihan (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Maral Dadvar (Germany/Iran, Germany), Diego Galafassi (Brazil/Sweden), Simon Divecha (Australia, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland/Austria, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Peter Duker (United States of America/Canada), Tim Forsyth (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Ethan Gordon (Australia/United States of America),

Gordon M. Hickey (Canada), Jennifer Hinton (United States of America, Sweden/Sweden), Mariaelena Huambachano (Peru, New Zealand/United States of America), Mulako Kabisa (Zambia/South Africa), Pratikshya Kandel (Australia), Sylvia Karlson-Vinkhuyzen (Sweden/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Hannah I. Korinth (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Germany/Germany), Juana Marino De Posada (Colombia), Handaine Mohamed (Morocco), Stefan Knauss (Germany), Rainer M. Krug (Germany/Switzerland), Elisa Morgera (Italy/United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Darcia Narvaez (United States of America), Jeanne Nel (South Africa/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Valerie Nelson (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Bathalifi Ngothoe (South Africa), Joyce Ojino (Kenya/South Africa), Timothée Parrique (France/Sweden), Henry Pitts (United States of America, Ireland/United States of America), Fabian Pröbstl (Austria/Germany), Nicholas Roskrug (New Zealand), Miles Richardson (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Darcy Riddell (Canada), Chris Riedy (Australia), Hens Runhaar (Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Arnim Scheidel (Austria/Spain), Sophia E. Schmid (Germany), Jonas Schroeder (Germany), Dorothea Schwarzer (Germany), Lynne Shannon (South Africa), Sèhankpon Tcheton (Benin/South Africa), Julia Teuchner (Germany), Cassady Turnbach (United States of America/Spain), Esther Turnhout (Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Paula Ugarte-Lucas (Spain), Alice Vadrot (Austria, France/Austria), Sergio Villamayor-Tomas (Spain), Sebastián Villasante (Argentina, Spain/Spain), Sandra Waddock (United States of America), Mariana Walter (Argentina, Spain/Spain), Christine Wamsler (Sweden, Germany/Sweden), Helen Wheeler (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Fern Wickson (Australia/Norway), David Wrathall (United States of America).

REVIEW EDITORS:

Carlos Alfredo Joly (Brazil), María Elena Zaccagnini (Argentina).

TECHNICAL SUPPORT UNIT:

Laurence Périanin, Camille Guibal, Anouk Renaud.

1. Authors are listed with, in parentheses, their country or countries of citizenship, separated by a comma when they have more than one; and, following a slash, their country of affiliation, if different from that or those of their citizenship, or their organisation if they belong to an international organisation. The countries and organisations having nominated the experts are listed on the IPBES website (except for contributing authors who were not nominated).

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Chapter 5

REALIZING A SUSTAINABLE WORLD FOR NATURE AND PEOPLE: TRANSFORMATIVE STRATEGIES, ACTIONS AND ROLES FOR ALL

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Chapter 5 presents quantitative and qualitative insights on actions and instruments around five strategies to bring about transformative change. Together these strategies address direct and indirect drivers (including underlying causes) of biodiversity loss and nature's decline (**Chapter 1**) with explicit attention to overcoming the specific challenges to transformative change (**Chapter 4**). The five strategies are: 1) conserving and regenerating places of value to nature and people; 2) driving systemic change in the sectors most responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline; 3) transforming economic systems for nature and equity; 4) transforming governance systems to be inclusive, accountable and adaptive; and 5) shifting societal views and values to recognize and prioritize the fundamental interconnections between humans and nature. An assessment of the literature that includes works examining deliberate transformative change for a just² and sustainable world suggests that some of these strategies have been studied more and literature aligns across contexts while others have more diverse or limited evidence behind them. Actions associated with the strategies serve as entry points for a set of intertwined, diverse and emergent pathways informed by theories of transformative change (**Chapter 3**) and guided by diverse visions for achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity and other global sustainability goals (**Chapter 2**). The chapter reflects the following key findings:

1 Compared to research on place-based conservation, on driving systemic change in the sectors most responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline and on shifting societal views and values, research on transforming economic, finance and governance systems has received significantly less attention (*well established*), suggesting a lack of focus on addressing indirect drivers of change {5.2}. Individual citizens, local communities, business, financial actors, national governments, educators and the scientific community pursue specific actions for transformative change together. Actions and actor groups interact in the

same time or space suggesting that actions are implemented in integrated ways, potentially because of their complementarity and synergistic effects.

2 Advancing inclusive place-based conservation where people already sustainably steward lands and waters is a key lever for transformative change (*well established*) {5.3.1}. This involves adjusting national legislation and other governance processes for protecting Indigenous Peoples and local communities' self-determination, human rights, customary tenure, knowledge and biocultural governance systems; advancing integrated spatial planning and regulation of land, freshwater and ocean uses; and listening to and collaborating with Indigenous Peoples and local communities to conserve remaining places of value to nature and people {5.3.1, 5.3.2, 5.3.5}. Indigenous Peoples manage or have tenure rights to about 40% of protected areas and ecologically intact landscapes across 87 countries (Garnett *et al.*, 2019). Recognizing the demonstrated long-term effectiveness of Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' biocultural approaches to conservation through legal and policy measures, as advocated for example by "territories of life" approaches, can support their ongoing caretaking role and remove lands from extractive pressures {5.3.1}.

3 Transformative change involves shifting from extractive to regenerative views, structures and practices whilst enhancing legal protection for biodiversity (*established but incomplete*) {5.3.4}. Reaching the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity means going beyond the conservation and restoration that the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework highlights and regenerating degraded social-ecological systems that contribute to nature's decline. Regeneration is where degraded social-ecological systems *revive themselves* through positive reinforcing processes² {5.3.4}. Conservation and restoration activities can help initiate these regenerative processes but typically suggest humans *doing things to nature*, whereas regeneration means humans *co-evolving as nature* {5.3.4}. It involves deepening relational values and responsibilities that nourish human-nature relationships by reviving local culture and nature, i.e., *biocultural* diversity {5.3.4}. This includes enhancing the legal protection of

2. See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>).

biodiversity and of all the multiple contributions of nature to people by protecting the rights of every human to a healthy environment, including Indigenous Peoples' rights, local communities' rights, women's rights and children's rights. Promising legal approaches towards considering more than instrumental values of nature include nature's rights and making ecocide an international crime {5.3.4}.

Multifunctional and regenerative land use approaches boost multiple uses of nature, evident in agroecological farming transitions that emphasize nature, healthy food production and physical and mental well-being. Increasing biodiversity, protecting native habitats and reducing external inputs in working landscapes has enhanced agricultural productivity by up to an average of 24%. Such improvements elevate employment levels, promote healthy livelihoods and foster a sense of identity and spiritual connection. The integration and promotion of multiple contributions of nature to people in planning and management decisions are thus crucial components of transformative change {5.3.4}.

4 Some governments already use innovative regulation, economic tools and technologies to drive change in sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline, but research has shown that implementation occurs at scales insufficient to change ongoing patterns (*well established*) {5.4.1, 5.4.2}.

The existing instruments to achieve global sustainability are applied at a scale that is insufficient for transformative change. Existing regulative policies (including 234 biodiversity-relevant taxes in 62 countries, 194 fees and charges in 50 countries and 39 tradable permits in 26 countries) have increased only marginally since 2010 {5.4.1} and do not challenge underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. Embedding technological innovations in transformative legal and planning frameworks, supporting long-term capacity enhancement and strengthening economic viability increases prospects for transformative change {5.4.2}. The reform of subsidies to economic sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature decline would release substantial funds to implement the sustainability agenda. Global public explicit subsidies to sectors directly driving nature's decline ranged within \$1.4 and \$3.3 trillion for 2023, depending on the source, and they create losses that exceed \$10.7 trillion (inflation-adjusted to 2023) in externalities {5.4.3}.

5 Triggers and incentives for change come from civil society among other actor groups (*well established*) {5.4.4}. Civil society experiments with social innovations and contests activities that threaten local environments. Social innovations result in nature-supporting activities in the agrifood, tourism and forestry sectors. Socio-environmental mobilizations (studied in 2,802 cases) provide evidence of civil society contestation of 46,955 threats to 13 of the 23 targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Most mobilizations (54%)

resulted in reforms (e.g., technical solutions, regulation enforcement, compensation), about one fourth (27%) resulted in repression and violence against civil society and only 19% resulted in the withdrawal, cancellation or temporal suspension of the activity responsible for environmental impacts {5.4.4}. Supporting social innovations, protecting socio-environmental initiatives from multiple burdens and rights violations, coordinating actions among different actor groups and developing mechanisms that support feedback processes between policies and social actions will amplify the contribution of civil society to transformative change.

6 A diverse mix of policy and governance actions at different scales are available for facilitating a just transformation toward sustainable economic development and human well-being (*established but incomplete*) {5.5}.

International trade is largely handled by the for-profit sector, with current global supply chains encouraging unsustainable sourcing and overproduction. If carefully designed, international agreements and complementary measures in production and consuming countries have the potential to regulate global supply chains to reduce excess consumption and ecological footprints and thus promote pro-nature production and trade. Because economic activities remain coupled with environmental pressures, the pursuit of economic growth in already-rich nations exacerbates ecological overshoot and threatens sustainable development in poorer regions. Selective downscaling of production and consumption in high-income and high consuming countries and by certain actors could be effective to lower the overall ecological footprint, accounting for complementary governance functions {5.5.2}. Instruments such as increased taxes or fines on nature-damaging activities, or binding policies regulating pollution or ecosystem restoration and policies benefiting the not-for-profit sector are options for just transformations to sustainable wellbeing economies. Not-for-profit models (e.g., consumer cooperatives, collective forms of resource sharing) aim to avoid trade-offs between investor interests and social and environmental benefits {5.5.2}.

7 Revising goals, metrics and indicators of progress can lead to diverse valuation of nature promoting new economic development paradigms that centre justice, inclusion, resilience and sustainability (*established but incomplete*) {5.5.4}.

Widely used measures of economic growth, such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and even the Human Development Index do not account for nature's non-marketed contributions and values. Alternative measures integrating other economic, social (including cultural) and environmental dimensions are available to measure progress. These measures either adjust the GDP measure (e.g., Green GDP), replace it (e.g., Happy Planet Index), or supplement it to account for nature's contributions to economic wellbeing (e.g., System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounts)

{5.5.4}. Assuring the inclusion of nature in measures of national incomes and wealth and in global financial flows will elevate biodiversity and nature as central criteria in private and public investments. Compliance with these obligations is tied to transparency, monitoring and institutional arrangements that evaluate and enforce actors' accountability, as proposed in frameworks, tools and standards such as those developed by the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD), among others {5.5.4}.

8 Reconfiguring institutional structures for transformative change entails reconfiguring the role of sectors and actors representing non-sustainable practices while recognizing and including advocates of the relational and intrinsic values of nature (established but incomplete) {5.6.1, 5.6.2}. Higher representation of balanced values in advocacy for nature and biodiversity, and inclusion of diverse knowledge systems² and stewardship in decision-making processes related to land use, sea use and resource use is a strong entry point for breaking-up sectoral silos. Inclusion of such values also counters the vested interests of producers and related business actors. A stronger integration of multilateral collaboration and revision of decision-making procedures (e.g., qualified majority votes, new forms of representation) are important factors for overcoming policy lock-ins and misfits {5.6.3}. Effective solutions for governing transnational sustainability challenges entail complementary initiatives in producing and consuming countries, across levels and governance networks. The creation of governance structures that reflect global interdependencies and incorporate the plurality of views related to nature, knowledge systems and voices provide a powerful lever for strengthening equity and a perceived responsibility {5.6.3, 5.6.2}. Genuine public participation in governmental processes and targeted collaboration between different affected and responsible stakeholder groups provide opportunities for society to pivot in the direction of just and sustainable transformation pathways {5.6.2}.

9 Iterative processes of planning, monitoring, evaluation and adaptive learning in nature-related governance support actions for transformative change when actors and institutions are held accountable and continually reflect on their own actions, responsibilities and underlying values (established but incomplete) {5.6.3, 5.6.4}. Including different stakeholders and their diverse knowledge systems in the planning, implementation and evaluation of processes that directly and indirectly govern resource-, land- and sea-use change on all levels, increases perceived responsibility and acceptance. Participatory experimentation, including co-creation, co-monitoring and co-evaluation of projects (including citizen science), provides the ability to reflect the interests and needs of those affected

and makes transformative change processes more equitable, sustainable and effective {5.6.4}. To guide targeted action, monitoring and evaluation need to go beyond a focus on ecological impacts and identify advances and shortcomings across the whole policy process. Transparent and inclusive review processes enable all actor groups to genuinely participate in evaluation processes and foster mutual learning {5.6.2}. Increasing flexibility of institutional mandates and budgeting, while incentivizing solution-oriented initiatives and promoting networks and collaboration, empowers governmental and private agents to find innovative solutions to overcome institutional lock-ins (institutional entrepreneurship) {5.6.1, 5.6.3, 5.6.4}.

10 Strengthening connections with and living as nature is a powerful driver for transformative change (established but incomplete) {5.7.1}. Deepening emotional and relational ties between people and nature supports individual and collective engagement in nature conservation, extending beyond simple access to nature. Encouraging multifaceted engagement with nature through integrated measures, such as incorporating nature-connectedness into education curricula, health and spatial planning, helps cultivate recognition that humans are part of nature and can live as nature {5.7.1, 5.7.4}. Shifting societal views and values alongside transforming cultural narratives and norms around production and consumption fosters a sustainable and just future {5.7.2}. Promoting arts programmes that celebrate nature furthers such cultural shifts. Additionally, supporting Indigenous practices for nature connectedness, and co-creating relational, living-as-nature visions and values enhances these shifts. Comprehensive approaches that address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, e.g., disconnection from and domination over nature and people, foster a culture of care that values nature and social justice.

11 Transformative learning and knowledge co-creation are central to efforts that foster sustainable futures and biodiversity conservation (established but incomplete) {5.7.4, 5.7.5}. Educational approaches, including citizenship education and social and emotional learning, play a critical role in fostering ecoliteracy and active engagement in sustainability practices. Whether provided by formal institutions or based on Indigenous and local knowledge, education supports collective action and the co-creation of relational, living-as-nature visions and narratives, driving the paradigmatic shift needed for effective biodiversity stewardship and justice. Transformative learning spaces integrate inner and outer dimensions of transformation and help people reconnect with themselves, others and nature and/or (re)learn ways of living as nature. Transformative learning emphasizes experiential and action-oriented learning strategies, fostering critical reflection and the development of new capacities and behaviours

needed to address complex social-ecological challenges and to promote a thriving, equitable and resilient future. For example, research in sustainable production of coffee and in establishing a circular economy more broadly has found that transformation in mindsets and values towards sustainable supply chains is supported through collective learning across individuals, sectors and the broader systems {5.7.4}. Knowledge co-creation, involving Indigenous Peoples and local communities, professionals, scientists, artists, grassroots groups and citizens is central to educational and learning processes. Decolonizing and promoting pluralism in all research and action is critical for equitable knowledge creation and challenging relations of domination. Recognizing the value of Indigenous as well as local and scientific knowledge systems challenges dominant beliefs and values of control and accumulation, while transformative learning promotes a cultural transition towards regenerative practices and sustainable worldviews {5.7.5}.

12 Transformative pathways always require the combination of multiple actions and occur when diverse actors work collectively to implement an integrated and purposive set of actions associated with multiple strategies for transformative change (established, but incomplete) {5.8}. Transformative pathways entail overcoming context-specific challenges related to vested interests that undermine planning, implementation, monitoring and learning processes for a sustainable future. Transformative pathways combine

actions from plural and diverse strategies to shape future outcomes while adhering to the principles of equity and justice, pluralism and inclusion, respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships and adaptive learning and action {5.8; 5.9}. Most existing options for actors have predominantly focused on instrumental values of nature. Their expansion to include options that reflect relational and intrinsic values of nature is visible in specific examples that highlight “rights and economics”, “subsidies and conservation measures” and “agroecological transitions.” Such examples highlight the role of transformative learning and illustrate that diverse entry points are available for collaborative action across actor groups to initiate changes in entrenched views, structures and practices {5.8.1, 5.8.2}.

5.1 INTRODUCTION

There is a rapidly closing window of opportunity for actions to secure global sustainability². Without urgent action, effects of global environmental challenges and crises, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution, will undermine nature’s contributions to people², worsen water and food insecurity and increase the risks of pandemics (Chapter 1). To address biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, the Transformative Change Assessment emphasize the importance of integrated approaches² to the triple planetary crisis of biodiversity loss, climate change²,

pollution and other related challenges². **Chapter 5** takes an integral approach to assessing the diversity of actions and actors² informed and inspired by different worldviews² and knowledge systems², following the principle of pluralism and inclusion (**Chapter 1**). It is the context-specific combination of these options in pathways that facilitate the emergence of transformative change², and hence enable a shift of interdependent views², structures² and practices² to overcome direct and indirect drivers² and underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. The chapter builds on the conclusions of the IPBES Global Assessment (2019) and assumes that effective interventions for transformative change are based on incentives, cross-sectoral cooperation, pre-emptive action and decision-making aimed at increasing resilience through integrative, inclusive, accountable and adaptive governance. Drawing on the IPBES Values Assessment (2022a), this chapter further recognizes that transformative change entails moving away from predominant views and values² that emphasize short-term and individual material gains to nurturing sustainability-aligned views and values across society, a move that can be partly achieved through a shift in societal goals and norms.

Drawing on a quantitative and qualitative assessment of existing knowledge derived from a corpus of more than 4.2 million documents assembled by this assessment in addition to proceedings of dialogue workshops focused on Indigenous and local knowledge, the chapter identifies five broad strategies for addressing direct and indirect drivers and underlying causes² of biodiversity loss and nature's decline (**Chapter 1**), as well as challenges to transformative change (**Chapter 4; Sections 5.1 and 5.2**). The strategies reflect different theoretical entry points for transformative change (**Chapter 3**). They build on the approach followed by the IPBES Global Assessment (2019), based on the IPBES conceptual framework, for direct and indirect drivers when distinguishing actions to conserve (**Strategy 1**), to address direct (**Strategy 2**) and indirect drivers (**Strategies 3 and 4**) as well as underlying causes (**Strategy 5; Chapter 1, Figure 1.3**). More specifically, **Strategy 1** identifies urgent actions needed for conserving remaining biodiversity and regenerating places of value for people and nature² that have been degraded (**Section 5.3**). **Strategy 2** addresses short-term actions to bring about change in the sectors most directly driving biodiversity loss and nature's decline (i.e., land use change, direct exploitation, climate

change, pollution and invasive alien species) (**Section 5.4**). **Strategies 3 and 4** explore medium-term actions to influence indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, focusing on transformation² of economic systems (including finance, **Section 5.5**) and governance institutions² (**Section 5.6**). **Strategy 5** addresses the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline by identifying actions for shifting individual and societal views and values to better align them with global sustainability goals. These strategies can be combined in different pathways to transformative change (**Section 5.7**). The strategies lead to transformative change when addressed in an integrated way, adhering to principles of equity² and justice, pluralism and inclusion, respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships and adaptive learning² and action (**Chapter 1**).

The strategies and actions are interdependent and associated with different actors (**Section 5.2**). For example, shifts in societal views and values (**Section 5.7**) create space for more inclusive governance² (**Section 5.6.2**) and greater interest in alternative economic models (**Section 5.4.2**). **Chapter 5** illustrates potential leadership roles for different actor groups², individuals and collectives and considers the alliances and coalitions needed to overcome path dependencies and institutional lock-ins. Actions from different strategies can be woven together in pathways² inspired by diverse visions² that emphasize the conservation, restoration² and sustainable use of biodiversity, good quality of life² and sustainable development² for all (**Chapter 2**). Pathways to sustainability are dynamic, emergent, inherently

uncertain and unpredictable and are contingent upon a sequence of actions operationalized by a range of actors and actor coalitions from different actor categories which are critical to nurture and amplify the impacts of actions with transformative potential² (**Figure 5.2**). In this sense, pathways are not blueprints for how the future will unfold, but rather purposive courses of actions, from short-term to long-term, leading to broader and sustained transformation (Ferguson *et al.*, 2013; Wise *et al.*, 2014).

The chapter illustrates how strategies aimed at phasing out the views, structures and practices² associated with the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline can create synergistic forces with strategies that empower sustainable and regenerative ways of viewing and interacting with the world at individual, collective and systems levels (**Chapter 3**). The chapter includes case studies and examples of actions spanning time frames, spatial scales², groups, sectors, regions and cultural contexts (**Table 5.1**). These purposively selected examples however only illustrate effects and roles of individual actions that will need to be combined in context-specific pathways to unfold their transformative potential (**Figure 5.2**).

The following sections include a quantitative analysis of the corpus of literature (referred to hereafter as assessment corpus) and of the corpus of literature on case studies (referred to hereafter as case corpus) (**Section 5.2**) assembled by the authors of this assessment. A brief overview of the five strategies and associated actions

Table 5.1 Overview of case studies in Chapter 5 illustrating potential roles for four actor groups in implementing options that contribute to transformative change when combined with other options in context specific pathways.

Private sector	Social movements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beenup Mine Site, Australia (Strategy 3; Section 5.5.4; Annex 5.2) • Patagonia natural clothing company, United States of America (Strategy 3; Section 5.5.2) • Business for Nature, global (Strategy 3) • We Sea, Jealsa's Corporate Social Responsibility programme, global (Strategy 3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IPCA, Great Bear Rainforest, Canada (Strategy 1) • Chipko movement, India (Strategy 2) • Unión Trabajadores de la Tierra, Argentina • Fridays for Future, global (Strategy 2) • Universal Declaration for the Rights of Mother Earth², global (Strategy 5)
Community-led initiatives	Government initiatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sacred Groves, India (Strategy 1) • Amazigh argan oil cooperatives, Morocco (Strategy 1) • Community forestry, Nepal (Strategy 1) • Certifying environmentally friendly farming, Japan (Strategy 4, Action 4.4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fisheries subsidies reform, New Zealand (Strategy 2; Section 5.4.3) • Lafkenche Act, Chile (Strategy 2; Section 5.4.3) • National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans, global (Strategy 4) • Green Minds, United Kingdom (Strategy 5) • European Union agricultural policy, European Union (Strategy 4) • Pachamama, Rights of Nature in Constitution, Ecuador (Strategy 5)

(Sections 5.3 to 5.7), further elaborated in the annexes (Annexes 5.1 to 5.6), and a consideration of diverse pathways to transformative change (Section 5.8; Annex 5.7) are also provided.

5.2 A GLOBAL REVIEW OF STRATEGIES AND ACTORS OF TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE FOR SUSTAINABILITY

The number of research publications on transformative change for sustainability at the global scale is about one hundred times larger than the number of those featuring case studies. This conclusion is based on the frequency analysis² of 566 key terms (related to 26 actions, grouped into five strategies) in the titles and abstracts of two

corpora: the assessment corpus (comprising approximately 4.2 million documents related to transformative change and nature) and the case corpus (a subset of 45,000 case studies from the assessment corpus). Thus applied research focusing on case studies largely lags behind theoretical works at the global scale. Place-based conservation actions (Strategy 1; 28% of documents in the assessment corpus and 33% in the case corpus), changing direct drivers (Strategy 2; 30% of documents in the assessment corpus and 30% in the case corpus) and shifting societal views and values (Strategy 5; 31% of documents in the assessment corpus and 32% in the case corpus) are strategies that have received more attention than the two strategies addressing indirect drivers of change by transforming economic systems (Strategy 3; 13% of documents in the assessment corpus and 16% in the case corpus) and governance systems (Strategy 4; 10% of documents in the assessment corpus and 18% in the case corpus; Figure 5.2). The actions described in Chapter 5 represent a small, and potentially biased, subset of actions with

Figure 5.3 Dendrogram comparing the percentages of occurrence in the literature of instruments across actions and strategies between the assessment corpus and the case corpus.

The line thickness in the dendrogram depicts the proportion of occurrences of 566 terms for instruments organized in 22 actions and five strategies in the titles and abstracts of 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus and 45,037 documents in the case corpus. Occurrences in the assessment corpus and case corpus are represented on top of each other, with the smaller one on top. If the occurrences in the two corpora are similar, the case corpus is depicted on top. Percentages under the names of the strategies indicate the proportion of occurrence of any instrument in the two corpora.

transformative potential, as only 8% of documents in the assessment corpus and 24% of documents in the case corpus include at least one of the terms used to search for the 26 assessed actions. This limitation makes it difficult to

reach universal conclusions and implies that other actions with transformative potential also exist. In both corpora, there is a high overlap between all actions, suggesting that they are interrelated and often implemented in integrated

Figure 5.4 Heatmaps of an indicator for the co-occurrence of terms relating actor groups and actions for transformative change.

The analysis of the two corpora of literature calculated the number of documents containing 566 terms for instruments (organized in 5 strategies and 26 actions) and 316 terms for actors (organized in 17 actor groups and 4 actor categories) in their title and abstract. The indicator is calculated by dividing the number of co-occurrences found by the maximum number of potential co-occurrences in a cell, i.e., the minimum of the number of hits in the two groups. The number can be interpreted as the proportion of existing links, among all possible links. (A) Heatmap of differences in co-occurrence between the case corpus and the assessment corpus. Darker colours represent higher levels of co-occurrence in the case corpus than in the assessment corpus. (B) Heatmap of co-occurrence in 4,654,669 documents in the assessment corpus. Darker colours represent higher co-occurrence. (C) Heatmap of co-occurrence in 45,037 documents in the case corpus. Darker colours represent higher co-occurrence. See data management report on strategies for details³.

ways, potentially because of their complementary and synergistic effects (Figure SM.5.2 in Annex 5.1).

The assessment of the frequency of occurrence of 316 terms for actors (organized in 17 actor groups and four actor categories, e.g., civil society, private sector, government sector and communicators and knowledge holders) in the title and abstract of the two corpora was used to assess the different level of engagement of actors with transformative change (Annex 5.1). The ‘Communicators and knowledge holders’ actor group – and especially the ‘scientific community’ – are the ones most featured in the literature, potentially indicating a bias among scientists towards representing their contributions and/or collaborative work in articles (40% in both corpora). In contrast, terms for actors in the ‘government’ category are the least featured (14% versus 13%), suggesting low past engagement of the public sector in transformative actions. Most actor groups co-occur in the two corpora, independently of whether they

belong to the same category of actors, implying that there is a wide potential for interactions among actors and coalitions (Annex 5.1).

Almost all actions and all groups of actors co-occur, but some co-occurrences are more frequent than others, as shown by darker colours in the cells of Figure 5.4. Individual citizens, local/regional governments, education and scientific communities display high co-occurrence with place-based actions (Strategy 1; upper lines in Figure 5.4-A). Business and the scientific community display high co-occurrence with changing direct drivers (Strategy 2). Individual citizens, local communities, national government, and the education community also display high co-occurrence with actions changing direct drivers in the case corpus (Figure 5.4-C). A similar overall pattern of actions and actors’ co-occurrence is found for transforming economic systems (Strategy 3), with donors/foundations and financial actors showing higher levels of co-occurrence with actions oriented to transform economic systems in the case study than in the assessment corpus. Individual citizens, local communities, businesses, national governments, education and scientific communities

3. Review of instruments, actions, and strategies for transformative change (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10264135>).

overlap with actions oriented to shifting societal views and values (**Strategy 5; Figure 5.4-A**). Individual citizens, local communities, business, financial actors, national governments and the education and the scientific communities are actor groups showing higher levels of co-occurrence, with more actions in the case corpus than in the assessment corpus.

An in-depth analysis was carried out on a purposively selected subset of 391 initiatives with transformative potential drawn from the Transformative Change Assessment case study database compiled for this assessment (referred to hereafter as “case study database”). Initiatives were coded according to the strategy that best reflected them. The appearance of actor groups in each of the strategies was analyzed to get a more nuanced understanding of the interactions and collaborations

necessary to implement a strategy (**Figure 5.5**). This analysis classifies actors in two sets of clusters, based on statistically significant differences in levels of collaborations. Results suggest that leadership by different actors depends on the strategy. These categories do not fully overlap with the previous categorization, which also considered frequency counts³. The most common strategy in the selected sample was **Strategy 1**: place-based actions (based on 96 case studies), whereas the least common was **Strategy 3**: transforming economic systems (based on 27 case studies). A group of about 70 examples had no dominant strategy. For almost all analyzed cases, collaborations and alliances between different actor groups appear to be essential for implementation. Indeed, almost all documented initiatives show collaborations among several actor groups.

Figure 5.5 Interactions within a network of actors for cases of transformative potential.

The 318 cases were classified according to the strategies that served as entry point for transformative change. Each strategy shows two clusters of coalitions of actors that statistically seem to collaborate in the implementation of the respective strategy. Nodes represent actor groups (18 groups), where node size represents the number of cases in which the actor is listed and node colour represents the two main clusters in each analysis (i.e., within a strategy, actors depicted with the same colour are better connected among themselves than with actors of a different colour). Clustering was done using Louvain's algorithm for modularity (Blondel *et al.*, 2008). Line thickness indicates the number of cases in which two groups of actors co-occur.

5.3 STRATEGY 1: CONSERVING AND REGENERATING PLACES OF VALUE TO NATURE AND PEOPLE

The 2050 Vision for Biodiversity aims to achieve a world living in harmony with nature². The concepts of conservation and regeneration² in this strategy are conceptualized as being embedded in a relational paradigm (Gram-Hanssen *et al.*, 2022; Poelina *et al.*, 2022), which serves as a foundation for achieving that harmony. This is an example of a decolonial approach, needed for post-development place-based relationalities. It highlights the inseparable entanglement of natures and cultures² (S. West *et al.*, 2020) and of interconnected life forms across generations (Watene, 2016a; Whyte, 2021). Without these considerations, strategies risk replicating relations of domination² (Muller *et al.*, 2019). Redistribution of power², including ways of knowing and being, and disruption of vested interests² are important aspects of the transformative change addressed in this assessment. This strategy also assesses the literature that builds on the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022a) to conserve, restore and sustainably use biodiversity², as well

as corresponding targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 14, 15). These concepts are integrated into the broader goal of regenerating biocultural diversity. Regeneration is where degraded social-ecological systems *revive themselves* through positive reinforcing processes (Buckton *et al.*, 2023; J. Fischer *et al.*, 2024).

Conservation and restoration activities can help initiate these regenerative processes but typically suggest humans *doing things to nature*, whereas regeneration means humans *co-evolving as nature* (J. Fischer *et al.*, 2024). As such, biological and cultural systems are interconnected in regeneration, i.e., *entangled natures and cultures* (S. West *et al.*, 2020). Regenerative strategies that protect and promote both biological and cultural (biocultural) diversity simultaneously provide multiple co-benefits over time (Levis *et al.*, 2024). Indigenous perspectives are transformative for environmental management when they challenge the dominant assumptions of extractive and colonial societies (Huambachano, 2020; Muller *et al.*, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2018). **Strategy 1** therefore represents a transformative bio-cultural conservation approach with actions to conserve and sustain the places where people and nature are still flourishing with relational worldviews, governance structures and practices, while envisioning new legal protections for peoples and places through rights-based approaches and area-based conservation based on diverse values of nature. These actions are complemented by the establishment of

regenerative views, structures and practices in extractive land-use sectors, which are implemented through spatial planning and policies as a pathway to establish effective conservation of biodiversity across landscapes and seascapes across scales².

5.3.1 Action 1.1: Recognizing and conserving the “territories of life” – Indigenous Peoples and local communities are custodians of vital biocultural heritages

Indigenous Peoples manage or have tenure rights to about 40% of protected areas² and ecologically intact landscapes across 87 countries (Garnett *et al.*, 2019). Recognizing the demonstrated role of Indigenous Peoples and local communities² in conserving the biocultural resilience of these areas, described as ‘territories of life’² (Zanjani *et al.*, 2023) creates a myriad of positive social and ecological outcomes across regions, ecosystems and intervention types (Blackman *et al.*, 2017; Dawson, Carvalho, *et al.*, 2021; Fa *et al.*, 2020; Garcia *et al.*, 2022; S. T. Garnett *et al.*, 2018; IPBES, 2023; Martín-López *et al.*, 2020; Schleicher *et al.*, 2017; United Nations, 2021a). Additional recognition of ‘territories of life’ would cover at least one-third of intact forest landscapes globally and nearly one-third of areas considered key to reversing biodiversity loss and to storing carbon (Zanjani *et al.*, 2023). Effective conservation of Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ territories is advanced when accompanied by legal protection of customary and collective tenure rights, implementation of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Peasants and Other People Working in Rural Areas (UNDROP) at the national level, as applicable (Garnett *et al.*, 2018; Knox, 2018a; Morgera & Nakamura, 2021; Oldekop *et al.*, 2016) and recognition of biocultural governance and knowledge systems (Mansuy *et al.*, 2023; Tauli-Corpuz *et al.*, 2020). Legal protection of rights and territories together can be an effective approach to resisting territorial pressures of industries, including agriculture, forestry, fisheries, livestock industries, mining and oil and gas, that negatively impact on the environment and human rights² (Agrawal & Redford, 2009; Christoplos *et al.*, 2009; Ferraro & Hanauer, 2011; Howe *et al.*, 2014; Mbaria & Ogada, 2016; Scheidel *et al.*, 2023). Recognizing views, structures and practices that deeply connect humans with nature over generations supports biodiversity² (Conversi, 2021; IPBES, 2019, 2022a; Ortiz-Prado *et al.*, 2021; Purvis *et al.*, 2018; Reed *et al.*, 2024). The protection of human rights and tenure recognition can be implemented through new forms of equitable co-governance and power-sharing (Makagon *et al.*, 2014; Maxwell *et al.*, 2020; Tauli-Corpuz *et al.*, 2020) in an ‘ethical space’, where multiple ways of knowing are recognized (Buxton *et al.*, 2021; Ermine, 2007).

5.3.2 Action 1.2: Enhancing legal protection for biodiversity through protecting human rights, recognizing nature’s rights and preventing ecocide

Legal protection of biodiversity can be enhanced through the protection of internationally recognized human rights, including the right of every human to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment (Bennett *et al.*, 2024; Knox, 2018b; UNGA, 2022); Indigenous Peoples’ rights (Knox, 2018b; Morgera, 2019; United Nations, 2020); local communities’ rights (De Schutter, 2012; Fakhri, 2024); women’s rights (Boyd, 2023); and children’s rights (Knox, 2018a; Morgera, 2024; Shields *et al.*, 2023; UNCRC, 2023). Legal recognition of these rights can change the perception of the importance of biodiversity for the realization of multiple policy goals (Reber *et al.*, 2022). Human-rights approaches provide an existing framework for reducing the disproportionately negative impacts of biodiversity loss on individuals and groups in situations of vulnerability that are identified by researchers as environmental injustices (N. J. Bennett *et al.*, 2022), empowering groups in vulnerable situations (N. J. Bennett *et al.*, 2023), enhancing compliance with law (Koh *et al.*, 2022) and clarifying the accountability of public authorities and private companies (N. J. Bennett *et al.*, 2024; Morgera, 2018). Human rights have been increasingly recognized as crucial to support transformation in biodiversity governance (Ituarte-Lima, 2023; Lombard *et al.*, 2022; Morgera, 2024; Switzer *et al.*, 2022; Webster & Morgera, 2021).

A number of experts also suggest that the legal protection of biodiversity can be enhanced through nature’s rights (Guayasamin *et al.*, 2021) and through recognizing ecocide² as a crime (Higgins *et al.*, 2013). Rights of nature is increasingly seen as an emerging legal paradigm based on diverse ecological values (Guayasamin *et al.*, 2021; Hsiao, 2012; Magallanes, 2018; Wesche, 2021) to overcome western and neoliberal legal models that can prioritize individual over collective wellbeing (O’Donnell *et al.*, 2020). Although its normative content remains the object of debate and its effectiveness remains to be fully proven (Bétaille, 2019; Guim & Livermore, 2021), and its implementation ultimately relies on contextual co-development. Currently less than 0.01% of the assessment corpus links rights of nature to transformative change and only 14 of the collected 881 visions (1.5%) (**Chapter 2**) focus on rights of nature (for an overview see Annex 5.1; Action 1.1 in Annex 5.2). Another approach suggested by some scientists is the international recognition of ecocide as an environmental crime. Ecocide refers to severe and either widespread or long-term environmental harm that is caused by “unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of such

harm” (Higgins *et al.*, 2013). A transformative action would be to require by law immediate measures to conserve and restore biodiversity as a matter of human rights, nature’s rights and/or prevention of ecocide. The prohibition of ecocide could provide an additional layer of legal accountability and challenge vested interests.(Higgins *et al.*, 2013; Lindgren, 2018; Sands *et al.*, 2021).

5.3.3 Action 1.3: Basing conservation on diverse values of nature to achieve inclusive biodiversity protection

Protected areas represent a primary approach (Bailey, 2023; Gurney *et al.*, 2023) to achieving Target 3 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework: to conserve 30% of lands, waters and seas by 2030 (Lessa *et al.*, 2021). However, some protected areas have displaced

peoples, disregarded Indigenous Peoples’ and local communities’ customary tenure and knowledge systems and led to human rights violations (Tauli-Corpuz, 2016; United Nations, 2021b). Protected areas, alongside other area-based conservation measures, can generate multiple and diverse values (Bernard *et al.*, 2014; IPBES, 2022a) that support biodiversity conservation² while upholding human rights and social safeguards and respecting worldviews and governance approaches (Dudley *et al.*, 2018). In particular, conservation designations can be transformative by recognizing the pluralistic values of Indigenous Peoples and local communities and their governance systems (Fa *et al.*, 2020; Indigenous Circle of Experts, 2018; Mansuy *et al.*, 2023; Maxwell *et al.*, 2020; Townsend, 2022). Indigenous – and locally – led biocultural approaches to conservation provide demonstrated long-term sustainability and socioeconomic co-benefits (Garnett *et al.*, 2018; Raymond *et al.*, 2010; Reyes-García *et al.*, 2023; Vigilante *et al.*, 2017). For example,

Figure 5.6 **Protect all life.**

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the Amazigh argan oil cooperatives in Morocco provide a compelling example of how cultural revival, environmental management and economic empowerment², especially for women, can intersect to create transformative change (IPBES, 2023b; Annex 5.3). Achieving target 3 will necessitate investment in knowledge building and collaboration between modern science and Indigenous and local knowledge², adequate financial supports and removal of policy barriers² to designating conserved areas managed by Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Tran *et al.*, 2020). This includes protecting human rights to avoid relations of domination persisting in conservation (Morgera, 2019; Tauli-Corpuz *et al.*, 2020; Youdelis *et al.*, 2021).

5.3.4 Action 1.4: Shifting extractive land-use systems to regenerative views, structures and practices that restore biocultural diversity

Conserving biodiversity involves regenerating degraded ecosystems (target 2 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework) used by sectors that are contributing to biodiversity loss and nature's decline – such as intensive agriculture (Campbell *et al.*, 2017; García-Vega *et al.*, 2024; Leadley *et al.*, 2022), mining (Murguía *et al.*, 2016; Sonter *et al.*, 2018; Ta & Campbell, 2023), forestry (Leadley *et al.*, 2022; Lindenmayer *et al.*, 2023), fishing (Morgera & Nakamura, 2021) and other direct exploitation of ocean organisms (N. J. Bennett *et al.*, 2022; Morgera & Lily, 2022). Regeneration is a place-sourced process of biocultural renewal (Mang & Haggard, 2016) that allows degraded social-ecological systems to *revive themselves* through positive reinforcing processes (Buckton *et al.*, 2023; J. Fischer *et al.*, 2024). It deepens relational values² and responsibilities between people and nature (Gordon *et al.*, 2022, 2023, 2024; Gosnell, 2022; Poelina *et al.*, 2022). This goes beyond restoring and sustainably using ecosystems because it establishes regenerative views, structures and practices in diverse sectors. Restoration is an activity that can help initiate these regenerative processes whereby social-ecological systems² revive themselves and evolve (J. Fischer *et al.*, 2024). However, it typically suggests humans *doing things to nature* whereas regeneration means humans *co-evolving as nature* (J. Fischer *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless, restoration activities can contribute to the broader goal of establishing 'regenerative cultures' (Knight *et al.*, 2024; Wahl, 2016; Woollorton *et al.*, 2022), which are place-embedded and in accordance with Indigenous Peoples and local communities' rights and worldviews (Gadgil *et al.*, 1993; James *et al.*, 2021; Watene, 2016). For example, landscape approaches (e.g., *Satoyama* and *Satoumi* in Japan) take an integrated view of the relationship between society, culture and ecosystems

(De Fries & Rosenzweig, 2010; Estrada-Carmona *et al.*, 2014; Kremen & Merenlender, 2018; Takeuchi *et al.*, 2016; Vonthron *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, a community forestry programme in Nepal integrates decentralized forest policy into local communities' needs, views and practices to restore and manage degraded forest areas (Ojha & Hall, 2023; Pandit & Bevilacqua, 2011). These practices maintain interrelationships between people and nature to support cultural values, sustainable production and biodiversity in agricultural landscapes (Jackson *et al.*, 2007; LaCanne & Lundgren, 2018; Moroder & Kernecker, 2022; Norris, 2008; Rey Benayas & Bullock, 2012; Scherr & McNeely, 2008) and productive seascapes (De Schutter, 2012). Transformative actions include policies to establish agroecological and regenerative food systems² that empower Indigenous Peoples and local communities through food sovereignty initiatives (Borbee *et al.*, 2023; Grenz & Armstrong, 2023; Huambachano, 2020; James *et al.*, 2021). These systems go beyond sustainability to actively improve the health² of ecosystems, communities and economies (James *et al.*, 2021), supporting livelihoods more closely connected to nature (Wahl, 2016). **Figure 5.6** depicts a Métis Vision of Regeneration symbolising the powerful connection and interconnectedness² between nature and humanity (The Communications Learning Circle of the Conservation through Reconciliation Partnership, 2023).

5.3.5 Action 1.5: Advancing integrated spatial planning based on diverse biocultural and regenerative values

Context-specific and collaborative land-use, spatial, freshwater and marine planning can safeguard biodiversity and nature's contributions to people when they are integrated across scales, sectors and stakeholders² (Harris *et al.*, 2022; Holness *et al.*, 2022; Shafer, 2015). Extending on **Action 1.5** in Annex 5.2, regenerative cultures that foster reciprocal relationships between people and nature can be cultivated through spatial design (Wahl, 2016), especially in cities and urban areas (Girardet, 2015). For example, permaculture is a design system based on Indigenous Peoples' biocultural knowledges (Mang & Reed, 2020) that regenerates relational values and builds urban agrobiodiversity (Hes & Plessis, 2014). Embedding biocultural and regenerative values into planning processes contributes to supporting collective human-nature wellbeing and changes economic incentives accordingly (M'sit No'kmaq *et al.*, 2021; Nikolakis & Hotte, 2022). This action enables legitimacy through genuine integration of communities and other rightsholders in planning to support equitable social interactions (Grantham *et al.*, 2010; Nikolakis & Hotte, 2022; Winkel *et al.*, 2015), challenging extractive interests (N. J. Bennett *et al.*, 2024) and incorporating diverse values of nature. Spatially this

involves complementing protected areas with buffer zones and corridors and enhancing species movement across landscapes (Perrin *et al.*, 2022; Shafer, 2015; Tablada *et al.*, 2022), while addressing sustainable use of biodiversity outside of protected areas (Barracough & Måren, 2022). In practice, this includes allocating resources to restoring critical ecosystem functions (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2012) across scales and integrating Indigenous and local knowledge (Buckton *et al.*, 2023; Convention on Biological Diversity, 2016; Redvers *et al.*, 2020) while

respecting human rights (Knox, 2018b; Lombard *et al.*, 2022; Morgera & Nakamura, 2021) and the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Peasants. Collaborative initiatives such as these are reflected in the vision of *buen vivir*² (Chapter 2) – a relational and adaptive way of living in harmony with nature (Chaves *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 5.7 **Actions to conserve and regenerate places of value to people and nature.**

The five actions in **Strategy 1** contribute to conserving and regenerating places of value for people and nature. The space inside the circle indicates actions conserving biocultural diversity where people and nature still thrive. The principles of transformative change help to expand the circle and to transform extractive views, structures and practices. Challenges to transformation indicate resistance or “push back”. The space outside the circle indicates actions to shift extractive land-use systems and to advance integrated spatial planning towards regenerative views, structures and practices.

5.4 STRATEGY 2: DRIVING SYSTEMIC CHANGE IN THE SECTORS MOST RESPONSIBLE FOR BIODIVERSITY LOSS AND NATURE'S DECLINE

The main direct drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline – i.e., land and sea use change, direct exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution and invasive alien species – are directly coupled to the challenge of unsustainable consumption and production patterns (**Chapter 4**). Economic and human activities are inherently dependent on nature and more than half of global Gross Domestic Product (\$58 trillion in 2022) is moderately to highly dependent on nature and on its contributions, with industries highly dependent on nature generating about \$13 trillion per year (15%) and industries moderately dependent on nature \$31 trillion per year (37%) (World Economic Forum, 2020). Biodiversity loss and nature's decline create material risks for countries and sectors. For example, biodiversity loss and nature's decline could result in the United Kingdom's GDP being between 6% lower than it would have been otherwise by 2030 under two scenarios² (domestic and international) and 12% lower under an antimicrobial resistance pandemic scenario (Ranger & Oliver, 2024). The assessed literature on transformative change largely discusses regulation, innovative economic tools and technological innovations² as actions to drive change in sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline (**Section 5.2**). However, recent IPBES work suggests that, when used in isolation, actions such as regulation, innovative economic tools and technology may unintentionally reinforce the instrumental values² that contribute to biodiversity loss and nature's decline (Pascual *et al.*, 2022). These actions are most effective when combined with strategies that focus on transforming economic systems, explained in **Strategy 3**, and governance systems, explained in **Strategy 4** (Pascual *et al.*, 2022).

5.4.1 Action 2.1: Regulating direct exploitation of organisms

The share of investments by the private sector in nature-based solutions represents only 17% of total investments globally, with therefore 83% from the public sector (UNEP, 2023b). The scope for private actors to transform their way of operating is shaped by the larger socioeconomic and cultural structures within which they are situated (Oliveira & Hecht, 2016; Phélinas & Choumert, 2017), for which targeted government support and regulation are indispensable in order to balance large-scale economic forces and structures, reduce barriers for change, and

catalyze sustainable and pro-biodiversity actions. Literature around the concepts of 'mainstreaming' and 'policy integration' refers to a number of approaches, actions and instruments to adjust regulatory frameworks, report on biodiversity and enforce change in economic sectors most responsible for nature's decline (see instruments for **Strategy 2** in Annex 5.3). For example, a large amount of literature has discussed the impact of different forms of agricultural production on land-use change, with a growing agreement on the benefits of agricultural practices that enable biodiversity to be maintained within agricultural landscapes (Baudron *et al.*, 2021) (**Section 5.8.2**).

Regulatory instruments include positioning biodiversity in legal requirements of user rights and concessions, conducting impact assessments for project approval and setting legal and fiscal penalties upon violation, (Rode *et al.*, 2023; Somarriba *et al.*, 2017). Examples include increased taxes on nature-damaging activities, binding policies regulating pollution or calls for ecosystem restoration (e.g., European Union Water Framework Directive or European Union Nature Restoration Law). The obligation of public reporting on sustainability is the most used regulative policy to promote adherence to specific biodiversity-friendly practices in the private sector, although it only affects large companies (Van Oorschot *et al.*, 2020) and their efficiency is debated (see instruments for **Strategy 2** in Annex 5.3). However, the number of regulative policies is low and has only increased marginally since 2010.

5.4.2 Action 2.2: Embedding technology in transformative frameworks

New technologies² contribute to transformative change when they contribute to profound shifts in production and consumption patterns. Indeed, the transformative potential of some useful technologies, such as smart electricity meters, might be exaggerated if their application does not consider how electricity is generated (see approaches for **Strategy 2** in Annex 5.3; **Chapter 4**) (Sovacool *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, technological innovations might not be appropriate when pre-existing technologies have positive impacts on nature, as with Indigenous or other forms of agriculture fostering biodiversity (Colchester, 1994). Various elements need to be considered to evaluate a technology transformative potential (Pentland *et al.*, 2022; Sen, 2014; Švarc & Dabić, 2021). For example, transforming energy use and electricity generation involves considering potential rebound effects², such as savings from energy efficiency improvements on energy-consuming services (Brockway *et al.*, 2021) or reliance on rare metals extraction that might reproduce colonial patterns (Kramarz *et al.*, 2021; Sovacool *et al.*, 2020). Communication technology comes as another example. Communication technology can act as means to support transformative

change through organizational use of the internet and social media by environmental movements (Ackland & O’Neil, 2011; Sovacool *et al.*, 2021), e.g., ‘Fridays for Future’ (Beckh & Limmer, 2022), but it has also been able to speed up pervasive and massive exposure of citizens to disinformation that directly threatens biodiversity and the environment (Lazer *et al.*, 2018; Treen *et al.*, 2020).

To be transformative, technological innovation should be embedded in legal and planning frameworks, such as intellectual property rights (Mallett, 2016). Moreover, technology “transfer” is widely considered a too narrow framing and there is a need for longer-term technological cooperation and capacity-building for technology innovation appropriate to local needs and economically viable (Heaton *et al.*, 1994; Mininni, 2017), in particular considering lack of (monetary and non-monetary) means of implementing new technologies in low-income countries.

5.4.3 Action 2.3: Financing for global sustainability

Current estimates⁴ of global biodiversity funding range between \$124 and \$143 billion per year in 2019 (\$135-\$156 billion inflation-adjusted to 2023), which is considered much less than necessary to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity. The global biodiversity funding gap is estimated at \$598-\$824 billion per year until 2030, depending on the source (Figure 5.8), with target 19 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework aiming to mobilize at least \$200 billion per year by 2030, through actions such as increasing biodiversity-related international financial resources, increasing domestic resource mobilization, leveraging private finance, stimulating innovative schemes, and enhancing the role of collective action, among others (see also Table 5.4). The global biodiversity financing gap undermines the effectiveness of existing instruments to

Figure 5.8 The economic landscape of global sustainability: interdependencies and funding gaps.

The figure illustrates the sharp contrast between economic sectors’ dependence (2) and impact (3) on nature, and between public investment in economic sectors driving nature’s decline (4) and biodiversity funding (6). The length of the arcs is adjusted to inflation to represent a share of the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2023 (estimated at \$105.6 trillion). (1) Global GDP in 2023 (\$105.6 trillion); (2) Global GDP moderately to highly dependent on nature in 2023 (\$58 trillion per year; WEF, 2020). (3) Externalities of sectors most responsible for nature decline estimated at \$10 trillion in 2021, inflation-adjusted to 2023 (\$10.7 trillion) (instruments for Strategy 2 in Annex 5.3). (4) Global direct subsidies to sectors most responsible for nature’s decline estimated between \$1.3 trillion and \$3.1 trillion in 2021, inflation-adjusted to 2023 (\$1.4 and \$3.3 trillion) (supporting material for Action 2.3 in Annex 5.3). (5) Global biodiversity funding gap (\$598-\$824 billion per year until 2030). (6) Global biodiversity conservation financing estimated between \$124-\$143 billion in 2019 (\$135-\$156 billion inflation-adjusted to 2023)⁴.

4. Literature review on harmful subsidies (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13789299>).

conserve, restore and sustainably use nature, with needs in poor and vulnerable regions. In this context, the United Nations Environment Programme has recently called for mobilizing all financial flows to maximize the potential of nature-based solutions,² including by leveraging private finance, promoting blended finance, implementing strategies for raising new and additional resources, and encouraging the private sector to invest in biodiversity (UNEP, 2023c).

The funding gap for nature could be partially closed by reforming subsidies to economic sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature decline, with target 18 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework aiming to reduce harmful incentives by at least \$500 billion per year. In the name of growth and development, governments heavily subsidize economic sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature decline, with overall estimations of global subsidies⁵ to the agriculture and livestock (\$610-\$939 billion), fisheries (\$48-\$61 billion), forestry (\$64-\$175 billion), fossil fuel (\$577-\$1390 billion) and road irrigation and irrigation infrastructure (\$311-\$938 billion) sectors ranking from between \$1.3 and \$3.1 trillion in 2021 (between \$1.4 and \$3.3 trillion inflation-adjusted to 2023) on direct subsidies (**Figure 5.8**; Annex 5.3). The OECD found that annually \$630 billion in environmentally harmful subsidies were given to farmers between 2020 and 2022 (Henderson & Lankoski, 2019; OECD, 2023). Since 2021, the total public funding for environmentally harmful subsidies has increased by 55% (UNEP, 2023c). Subsidies coupled with production or consumption encourage overproduction and overconsumption, leading to biodiversity loss and nature's decline, inequality² and market distortion (Kindvall *et al.*, 2022; Perez *et al.*, 2023), with subsidized sectors generating around \$10.7 trillion per year in externalities in 2022 (e.g., water pollution, soil degradation). National governments and international organizations (e.g., World Trade Organization) and multilateral frameworks (e.g., Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, Paris Agreement, 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development) include reforming environmental harmful subsidies, but progress has been limited (Dempsey *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, a sentiment analysis conducted to assess whether subsidies are presented as 'positive', 'neutral', or 'negative' in the literature show an increasing stabilization of positive sentiments towards subsidies (**Annex 5.3**). While subsidy reforms are politically challenging, key levers for meaningful subsidy reforms include redistributive policies to address the needs of those left in vulnerable situations due to reforms (Chancel *et al.*, 2022; Skerritt *et al.*, 2023), increasing policy coherence across sectors, global coordinated action (IMF *et al.*, 2022) and contextualisation and monitoring of multiple impacts (Bridle *et al.*, 2022). Examples of subsidies reform with strict sustainability criteria include examples from New

Zealand's fisheries seeking synergies in subsidies provided (Campling & Havice, 2013), Zambia's funds reallocation to climate smart agriculture and biodiversity conservation (González-Poblete *et al.*, 2020; Mweemba, 2018), or Mexico's development and application of an information system that allows federal government institutions to provide incentives to activities that protect nature while promoting the country's food sufficiency (Sarukhán & Ramírez Reivich, 2022). While governments can incentivize business action on nature through providing subsidies for nature-positive practices (**Strategy 3**), caution is required while taking action to reduce subsidies and support for actions that harm nature at the same time. Increasing the number of nature-positive subsidies will not be enough if nature-negative subsidies increase at the same time – or remain the same.

5.4.4 Action 2.4: Supporting civil society initiatives

Civil society, including the wave of youth environmental activism from 2019 onwards, uses different actions to drive change in sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline (De Moor & Wahlström, 2021; Sloam *et al.*, 2022). Citizens scrutinize companies' impact on nature, expose their shortcomings and fuel public debate on responsible and acceptable practices (Boiral *et al.*, 2018; Elmagrhi *et al.*, 2019). Civil society also experiments with social innovations, highlighting local actors' collective knowledge and action to lead deliberate change (Apostolopoulou *et al.*, 2022). For example, a purposively conducted systematic review of 100 empirical case studies of rural social innovations across Europe during 1970-2024 illustrates the variety of social innovation with potential to curb biodiversity loss and nature's decline (instruments for civil society in Annex 5.3). Around one third of the initiatives reviewed result in nature-supporting innovations in the agrifood (62%), tourism (44%) and forestry sectors (35%). Half of the biodiversity-supporting innovations (17 cases) are local, 16 are sub-national and one national. Civil society also contests private interests that directly threaten the local environment (Scheidel *et al.*, 2020; Thiri *et al.*, 2022; Walter & Wagner, 2021). An analysis of 2,802 social-environmental mobilizations occurring between 1992 and 2022 provides evidence of social contestation to threats to targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, where a threat is defined as a reported environmental impact (e.g., biodiversity loss, soil contamination, ground water degradation, or oil spills). This analysis showed evidence of a total of 46,955 threats to 13 targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework contested by socio-environmental mobilizations. A hierarchical cluster analysis⁶ classified cases into three distinctive groups

5. All figures are adjusted to 2023 US\$ billions.

6. Review of supporting civil society initiatives (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862423>).

according to their predominant outcomes: repression, reform and transformation (Figure 5.9; Box 5.1). The same threats also jeopardize the implementation of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous

Peoples, leading to landscape loss, livelihood loss and land dispossession (Scheidel *et al.*, 2023). Combining preventive mobilization, tactical diversity and litigation increases activists' success (Scheidel *et al.*, 2020).

Box 5 1 **Civil society initiatives: Prey Lang Community Network, Cambodia.**

The Cambodia Prey Lang Community Network was established in 2007 by local Khmer and Kuy Indigenous Peoples to protect Prey Lang Forest, Southeast Asia's last major lowland rain forest, which was threatened by illegal timber trade, agro-industries and mining concessions. The movement conducted regular forest patrols to stop illegal loggers and confiscate chain saws, used smartphones to collect data on forest crimes,

lobbied authorities and launched several campaigns that drew wide attention to their cause. Actions of the Network required changes in views, structures and practices. (Theilade *et al.*, 2021). For their substantial contributions to environmental protection, they were awarded the 2015 UNDP Equator Prize and the 2019 Energy Globe Award.

Given that most companies treat environmental issues in response to threats associated to other external actors (Addison *et al.*, 2019; Van Oorschot *et al.*, 2020), supporting and amplifying civil society initiatives can help dismantling harmful practices and promote new ways of thinking, organizing and doing (E. Bennett *et al.*, 2016). Inclusive governance processes and protection of environmental defenders from violence and rights violations (Butt *et al.*, 2019; Le Billon & Lujala, 2020; Scheidel *et al.*, 2023; Tran, 2023) alleviate the vulnerability associated with civil society action seeking transformative change (Blythe *et al.*, 2018). Governmental efforts to develop corporate due diligence policies and trade agreements conditional upon upholding the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and divestment campaigns targeting corporations involved in rights violations could all be entry points to increase the environmental impact of civil society initiatives.

largely dominated by references to just transitions², whereas references to innovative economic tools, financial systems reforms and new metrics of success are scarcer (**Section 5.2**). Alternative economic visions to mainstream nature and biodiversity are reviewed in **Chapter 2**. Common features of these approaches are the focus on conservation and sustainable use of nature and good quality of life and sustainable development², although they differ in the depth of change sought, the relative emphasis on nature and biodiversity, as well as related social aspects and the timescale that might be needed to reach results. Three main approaches emerge:

- 1) Green economy (including proposals for green growth, bioeconomy, and circular economy²;
- 2) Limits to growth (including steady-state economy, degrowth², and post-growth); and
- 3) Wellbeing within Planetary Boundaries (including proposals for an economy of the common good, doughnut economy and *buen vivir*) (**Annex 5.4**).

5.5 STRATEGY 3: TRANSFORMING ECONOMIC SYSTEMS FOR NATURE AND EQUITY

Power imbalances and inequities manifest in how economic and financial systems operate, lead to the decline of nature and biodiversity, and result in barriers and challenges to transformative change (**Chapter 4**). Economically powerful actors² pursue agendas based on private interests that are often at odds with sustainability, highlighting the need to address the complex interlinkages between inequity and the environment (Ceddia, 2020; Downey & Strife, 2010; Kenner, 2019). Financial institutions acknowledge that biodiversity loss and nature's decline constitute systemic risks to business, finance and national economies (Agarwala *et al.*, 2022; World Economic Forum, 2020), resulting in calls to fundamentally restructure economic and fiscal institutions (Piketty, 2020).

Transforming economic systems is one of the two less frequent strategies mentioned in literature, which is

5.5.1 Action 3.1: Mainstreaming innovative economic tools

Governments and business can create positive incentives to engage in conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, by the use of different economic instruments for example payment for ecosystem services², taxes, subsidies or tradable permits and other positive price signals (**Annex 5.3**) (DeBoe, 2020). For example, governments have implemented new financial incentives to support nature-friendly activities, such as the Environmental Land Management Scheme in England, designed to financially reward sustainable farmland management (Hurley *et al.*, 2022), or the government programme *Sembrando Vida* in Mexico, which economically compensates smallholders for planting trees. However, these instruments are often too small in scope, too poorly designed, or applied to bring about change at scale (Kolinjivadi *et al.*, 2023; Wunder *et al.*, 2020). Multiple examples of these subsidies exist across contexts, just one review identifies 163 nature-relevant

subsidies including for reforestation, agroecology or land conservation in 28 countries (OECD, 2021). Mainstreaming and integration of biodiversity in policies can be fostered through joint planning, including non-environmental sectors, revising institutional settings to coherently support biodiversity and sustainability, including through adaptive learning (Runhaar *et al.*, 2024) (see **Strategy 4**).

Companies also apply voluntary instruments to compensate for the additional costs associated with protecting nature, such as Payments for Ecosystem Services, or Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (Piñero *et al.*, 2020; Tedesco *et al.*, 2023). For example, private initiatives have been developed to support alternative farming and livestock keeping, such as the *Herenboeren* or the *Land van Ons* initiatives in The Netherlands, or the Grassland Alliance in the United States of America. These instruments can take decades to bring about change (Geels *et al.*, 2023), although their effectiveness can increase if they simultaneously address environmental, social and economic outcomes (Budiharta *et al.*, 2016; Klausner & Negra, 2020; Ostrom, 2009; Piñero *et al.*, 2020; Tedesco *et al.*, 2023).

5.5.2 Action 3.2: Supporting just transitions towards good quality of life

Economic growth represents a significant challenge for nature (**Chapter 4**). Because economic activities remain significantly coupled with environmental pressures (Charlier & Fizaine, 2023; Haberl *et al.*, 2020; Parrique *et al.*, 2019; Vadén *et al.*, 2020; Vogel & Hickel, 2023), the pursuit of economic growth in already-rich nations exacerbates ecological overshoot while threatening possibilities for sustainable development in poorer regions (Chancel *et al.*, 2022; Fanning *et al.*, 2022; Hickel *et al.*, 2022; Khalfan *et al.*, 2023). Selective downscaling² of production and consumption in high-income and high consuming countries and actors could be effective to lower the overall ecological footprint², accounting for complementary governance functions in producing and consuming countries (Hickel *et al.*, 2022; Kallis *et al.*, 2018). A diversity of actions, ranging from redistributing wealth (Chancel *et al.*, 2022), universal basic income (Van Parijs & Vanderborght, 2017) and localization of the economy (Hickel, 2022), to the promotion of the not-for-profit sector (Hinton, 2023), have been proposed for a just transition to sustainable wellbeing economies (**Annex 5.4**) (Fioramonti *et al.*, 2022). For example, universal basic income has been proposed to reduce consumption-driven spending as it could promote purposeful activities (Lawhon & McCreary, 2020; Van Parijs & Vanderborght, 2017), but there is no empirical evidence of the impact of a universal basic income on consumption, with some models actually suggesting that redistributing income to poorer groups might increase consumption and

emissions due to their higher carbon-intensive spending habits (Oswald *et al.*, 2021).

Many conventional economic approaches assume that private profit is necessary to motivate the efficient functioning of businesses. However, empirical evidence challenges this assumption by demonstrating the efficient functioning of not-for-profit companies and social enterprises (Blackwood *et al.*, 2012; Ko & Liu, 2021; Patten, 2017; Powell & Bromley, 2020; Salamon, 2010). Furthermore, measures such as progressive environmental taxes (Andersson, 2009; Van Parijs & Vanderborght, 2017) are one way to avoid the inadvertent increase in unsustainable consumption (Oswald *et al.*, 2021). Regulating profit has been proposed as a way to level the competition playing field for businesses to contribute to sustainability (Foster, 2014; Hinton, 2021; Hinton, 2020; Magdoff & Foster, 2011; W. Moore, 2014; Schnaiberg *et al.*, 2002). Not-for-profit models can avoid trade-offs between social and environmental benefits and investors' interests driving overconsumption. The transition of the clothing company 'Patagonia' from a for-profit to a not-for-profit structure evidences the power of the private sector for transforming economic systems (Agafonow & Perez, 2024; Khmara & Kronenberg, 2018).

5.5.3 Action 3.3: Reforming financial systems and institutions

Financial institutions have an outsized impact on nature (Global Canopy, 2021; Portfolio Earth, 2020) (**Chapter 4**) and reforming the financial system has been proposed as a way to relieve environmental pressures, particularly in low-income countries (Dasgupta, 2021). Such reforms imply mechanisms that facilitate socially and ecologically fair access to resources globally (Ocampo, 2017; Svartzman & Althouse, 2022) and new roles for Central Banks and other funders (Couppey-Soubeyran & Delandre, 2021; Dafermos *et al.*, 2021, 2022; Gabor, 2020; Thiemann, 2024). Ongoing and proposed actions to reform financial systems include regulating speculative financial instruments (Clapp & Isakson, 2018; Davis *et al.*, 2020), regulating global exchange prices (Dorninger *et al.*, 2021; Hickel *et al.*, 2022), reconsidering global debts and development assistance (Couppey-Soubeyran & Delandre, 2021; Hugé *et al.*, 2020), phasing out tax havens, taxing resource rents or eradicating corruption (**Annex 5.4**) (Dempsey *et al.*, 2020; Galaz *et al.*, 2018; Shin *et al.*, 2022). For example, the European Union financial regulation allows businesses and investors to identify sustainable economic activities, discourages greenwashing² and redirects financial flows towards sustainability (EU High-Level Expert Group on Sustainable Finance, 2019). Debt-for-nature-swaps provide powerful financial opportunities to conserve nature (Shandra *et al.*, 2011; Volz *et al.*, 2022), as exemplified by the sale

of blue bonds worth \$1 million per year for conservation of the Galapagos Islands, which enabled Ecuador to buy back about \$1.6 billion of the country's debt at 60% discount (Asian Development Bank, 2023). However, if not designed following the four transformative change principles²

(**Chapter 1**), such schemes may have unexpected social impacts on Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Hassoun, 2012; Macekura, 2016) or women (Hobbs, 2012). Reducing the acceptability of tax avoidance can generate income to cover the national biodiversity gap (Bird & Davis-Nozemack, 2018; Dempsey *et al.*, 2022).

Biodiversity objectives can be better achieved when aligning private and public financial flows for dual purposes. This entails mobilizing new finance for nature-positive outcomes, while ensuring that existing funding is not harmful to nature (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022b; IDFB, 2022). This requires new roles and responsibilities for finance and economic actors (e.g., ministries of finance, central banks, regulators or investors) to create enabling environments and incentives to transform the financial sector (Galaz *et al.*, 2018; IDFB, 2022). The process can also be improved by assessing the risk in both ways – environmental risks to the financial sector, and direct and indirect effects of the financial sector (e.g., through investments, loans and other financial flows) on increased environmental risks – which in turn create cascading effects that lead to systemic (financial and other) risk (Crona *et al.*, 2021). In short, there needs to be a deeper understanding by the financial sector of the feedback mechanisms and externalities between financial investments and the earth system, which cut across diverse sectors and dimensions (i.e., social, economic, environmental). Numerous initiatives have been proposed and could be undertaken and/or upscaled to reshape finance for nature including, for example, the development and implementation of new taxonomies (e.g., the EU green taxonomy) (Tettamanzi *et al.*, 2023), ensuring that loans and other financial tools are nature-positive. Other proposed initiatives include developing and mandating methodologies for risk assessments that consider the value of nature; encouraging and/or mandating disclosures of nature-related risks, impacts, linkages, dependencies and opportunities (e.g., TNFD) (Annex 5.4) and supporting networks of private and public initiatives to mainstream nature/biodiversity considerations (including risks and opportunities) into financial and economic risk assessments (e.g., The Network for Greening the Financial System). However, these actions taken in isolation will have limited transformative potential and need to be accompanied by changes in values and governance to support sustainable and equitable outcomes (see **Strategies 1, 4, 5**) and shift towards more sustainable economic and financial sectors (**Strategy 2; Annexes 5.3 and 5.4**). For instance, there is tenuous evidence that disclosing nature risk will automatically lead to redirecting finance away from environmentally harmful investments and activities (Irvine-Broque & Dempsey, 2023), pointing to

the need for a constellation of actions that, together, create enabling environments towards more sustainable pathways.

5.5.4 Action 3.4: Adopting metrics of success that focus on social, economic, cultural and environmental goals

The standard measure of economic growth, Gross Domestic Product, exclusively relies on marketed goods and services (Costanza *et al.*, 2009; Stiglitz, 2020) and more inclusive measures of success have been proposed (Fleurbaey, 2009; Raworth, 2017; Stiglitz *et al.*, 2009) (**Annex 5.4**). Proposed measures either adjust the standard GDP measure (e.g., Green GDP, Genuine Progress Indicator), replace it with indices accounting for human wellbeing and environmental impact (e.g., Happy Planet Index, Inclusive Wealth), or supplement it to account for nature's contributions (e.g., System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting, True Cost Accounting) (Coates *et al.*, 2020; FAO, 2023a; SEEA, 2012; UNEP, 2021) (**Figure 5.8**). Alternative measures to GDP allow for integration of nature into national accounts systems and/or provide different measures of success. For example, the Inclusive Wealth Report, which maps the inclusive wealth levels of 98% of the global population incorporating natural, human and produced capital, shows increasing global inequality in per capita natural capital since 1998 across countries (from Gini Index 0.67 in 1998 to 0.72 in 2019), which might lead countries of the world to competition for access to land, water and critical natural resources² that may trigger conflicts (UNEP, 2023a).

Frameworks are emerging to identify, measure, evaluate and act on business' relationships with nature, for example the ACT-D framework which entails acting, committing and transforming disclosure to drive high-level business actions on nature, or the LEAP framework, which involves locating, evaluating, assessing and transforming relationships with nature. Sector-specific tools and guidance materials are being developed to leverage natural capital accounting by assessing and disclosing businesses' nature-related risks (e.g., Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures, Global Reporting Initiative, UN SEEA EA for Ecosystem Accounting, Product Biodiversity Footprint) (Asselin *et al.*, 2020; Ingram *et al.*, 2024). Critical factors to successfully implement and scale up natural capital accounting by businesses include: i) identifying the link between nature outcomes and corporate activities, ii) translating strategic intent into on the ground action, and iii) creating incentives to support corporate decisions (Bebbington *et al.*, 2024) (**Box 5.2**).

Figure 5.10 System of Environmental Economic Accounting in the world.

Implementation in 2023 and earlier policy benchmark assessments by geographic region (upper panel). Compilation of System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting by countries (bottom left) and type (bottom right) in 2023. Source: United Nations (2023).

Box 5.2 Natural capital accounting by the private sector: Beenup mine site.

BHP is a commodities-focused enterprise centered on assets such as iron ore, coal, copper and potash. It closed and rehabilitated the Beenup mineral sands site in southern Western Australia, which represents the first natural capital account trial within the mining industry (WABSI, 2023). The mine started in 1997 but closed two years later due to technical difficulties. In 2003, rehabilitation and restoration remedial earthworks were completed to restore natural values as intended by local communities. The index for the site’s natural capital accounting was developed through scenarios – pre-mining (June 1991), mining (June 1999), rehabilitation (June 2005) and post

rehabilitation (June 2020) – aligned with those described in System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounts (SEEA-EA) (Keith *et al.*, 2020). Post rehabilitation, threatened fauna and flora species returned to the site, exceeding pre-mining numbers. The newly found fauna species were associated with wetland ecosystem creation. Currently, the Beenup site comprises around 500 ha of native ecosystems and 182 ha of grazing pasture. The site has restored nine ecosystem types, 15 vegetation communities and over 250 species (including rare and priority species) in a heavily disturbed and modified post-mining environment (Meney *et al.*, 2023).

5.6 STRATEGY 4: TRANSFORMING GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS TO BE INTEGRATED, INCLUSIVE, ACCOUNTABLE AND ADAPTIVE

Path-dependencies of unsustainable resource exploitation and land and sea use are stabilized by persistent relations of domination and a dominance of extractivist worldviews connected with unsustainable production and consumption patterns and corresponding knowledge systems (Chapter 4), leading to both inequalities and

injustices and resulting in biodiversity loss and nature's decline. The resulting institutional settings and power imbalances are central explanatory factors for institutional misfits² (Chapter 4; Figure 4.6) undermining the effective implementation of Strategies 1 to 3. Structural actions to support transformative governance² include four actions⁷ described in Figure 5.11 (Strategy 4 in Annex 5.5). These four actions represent entry points for adjusting dominant governance systems and increasing their priority and consideration for nature and biodiversity. The application of these actions is illustrated for National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) (Table 5.2), which are the main instrument for implementing the Convention for Biological

7. Literature review on governance (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862495>).

Diversity and are supported by international initiatives, such as the NBSAP Accelerator partnership.

5.6.1 Action 4.1: Strengthening biodiversity-related values in integrated governance across sectors

In multi-level, multi-actor governance settings, coherent support for nature entails integration across political sectors and levels that is leveraged through institutional adjustments and facilitating processes (Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen *et al.*, 2017; Sarkki *et al.*, 2016). Joint planning processes and connecting sector discourses² allow actors to position their targets and actions in national agendas (Cardona Santos *et al.*, 2023), develop integrated solutions (Fajardo *et al.*, 2021; Shih & Mabon, 2018), implement acceptable and practical standards (e.g., for fishing practices, Friedman *et al.*, 2018) and realize integrated visions incorporating Indigenous and local knowledge (Whitehorn *et al.*, 2019). The revision of policies in the sectors most responsible for direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline (**Strategy 2**) can be guided by a clear vision, a clear legal mandate, collaborative network structures and facilitated learning processes (Kivimaa & Mickwitz, 2009; Persson & Runhaar, 2018; Runhaar *et al.*, 2024). Actions to overcome power asymmetries in decision-making where it hampers positive impacts on nature include adjusting legal responsibilities and transparency (Zhu *et al.*, 2015), the allocation of resources (Sarkki *et al.*, 2016) and strengthening the role of environmental agencies in land/sea-use decisions, e.g., by changing approval procedures for environmental assessments (Kontić & Kontić, 2012). The example of the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy illustrates that agri-environmental measures can be an effective tool for strengthening biodiversity in agricultural landscapes and its transformative potential has been shown for instance through the changes in fallow land responding to changes in policy design (Röder *et al.*, 2024). However, this potential is hampered by an underrepresentation of environmental advocates in decision-making overshadowed by a dominance of interest groups (Brown *et al.*, 2019; Daugbjerg & Swinbank, 2016) and by missing transparency and constant policy redesign that undermine evaluation and learning procedures (Lakner *et al.*, 2021). Beyond increasing support and incentives for collaboration among sectors and actor groups, financial capacity can be mobilized by harnessing synergies² with other policies, including climate funds (Siddiqui, 2013) or agricultural policies (Dik *et al.*, 2023). Shocks create windows of opportunities for transformative change (Benessaiah & Eakin, 2021; Brundiers & Eakin, 2018), which can be used for strengthening pro-environmental behaviour and practices (Morse *et al.*, 2020; Wittmayer *et al.*, 2019), but depending on the context, shocks can also be used to weaken environmental policies

as has been observed during the COVID-19 pandemic (Powers *et al.*, 2021; Rocha *et al.*, 2021) and the Ukraine war (Pröbstl *et al.*, 2023; Vincent *et al.*, 2024).

5.6.2 Action 4.2: Engaging diverse actors in inclusive governance to increase responsibility to act on biodiversity

In order to overcome the relations of domination and marginalization of certain groups – particularly those providing sustainable worldviews (**Chapter 4**) – and to comply with the principles of equity and justice (**Chapter 1**), inclusive governance is essential. Inclusive biodiversity governance involves strategies for coalition-building (**Chapter 3**) and involves a variety of mechanisms designed to engage a broad range of stakeholders that represent a plurality² of views, structures and practices based on plural knowledge systems, including Indigenous and local knowledge, silent voices and non-human perspectives. Applying and combining participatory mechanisms strengthens equity, legitimacy and perceived responsibility and provides opportunities to pivot society in the direction of just transformation (Apostolopoulou *et al.*, 2022; Armitage *et al.*, 2020; N. Bennett *et al.*, 2019; Huntjens, 2021; Leventon *et al.*, 2019; Paloniemi *et al.*, 2015; Scoones *et al.*, 2020; Wamsler & Riggers, 2018). Examples of mechanisms of inclusive governance include public consultations, deliberative democracy, multi-stakeholder partnerships and consultations, community-based natural resource management, co-management of nature, gender-sensitive approaches, biodiversity councils and committees, citizen science programmes and rights-based approaches, including the recognition of Indigenous rights (Action 5.2 in Annex 5.6).

For successful outcomes of collaborative processes, it is critical that all actors (supported by facilitating agents, e.g., professional facilitators, governmental actors or local community members) work on generating trust and social capital in actor networks (Polman & Slangen, 2008). Increased stakeholder involvement does not necessarily lead to conservation success (Young *et al.*, 2013). Inclusive governance is considered effective when it leads to collective agreements (e.g., natural social contracts²) across members and levels of society to cooperate and abide by certain norms targeted at sustainability, equity and justice, with the associated rights and duties of care for nature and the well-being² of others (including future generations and all life on this planet) (Huntjens, 2021). This can be supported by community and citizen science in local contexts for monitoring and evaluating action on nature and biodiversity (Fritz *et al.*, 2019; Jacobs *et al.*, 2018; Pascual *et al.*, 2017), as well as by the evaluation of interventions according to social performance standards, anti-corruption measures and

auditing down to the local level (Chan *et al.*, 2017; Douglas, 2020; Pascual *et al.*, 2014). Equally, in the government-led development of National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (Table SM.5.1 in Annex 5.1), an inclusive process including Indigenous and local knowledge is essential to increase responsibility and awareness of multiple values of nature among stakeholders (Cardona Santos *et al.*, 2023; Prip, 2018). Effective communication and attention to perceptions and attitudes of local stakeholders build trust and enhance participation (Lyons, 2012; Mbaiwa & Stronza, 2011; Young *et al.*, 2013). Different groups might be mobilized and informed through various forms of media (e.g., new programmes, science programming such as Attenborough's Blue Planet, social media fact-checking) and through various mediating institutions e.g., schools, religious organizations, charities, civic society groups and 'biodiversity champions' to engage their communities.

5.6.3 Action 4.3: Securing collaboration and accountability through multilateral governance to address global interdependencies

In a globally integrated economy with unprecedented levels of trade, governing biodiversity loss and nature decline is linked to global value chains², finance flows and transnational interdependencies (**Strategy 3**) (Liu *et al.*, 2013). International collaboration can be strengthened by formally integrating currently fragmented bi- and multilateral agreements (Biermann, 2002; Jinnah, 2014), changing decision-making rules, such as moving from consensus to majority voting (Chasek, 2011), or redistributing resources and capacities across multilateral agreements (Albin & Druckman, 2017; Tolochko & Vadrot, 2021). Compliance mechanisms for agreements relevant for nature and biodiversity improve through inclusive representation of non-State actors (Duyck, 2015), incorporating different knowledge systems into planning, monitoring and evaluation for collaborative policy learning (Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen *et al.*, 2017), evolving political conditions (Carroll *et al.*, 2023) and specifying responsibilities and timelines (Koh *et al.*, 2022). Eventually, coherence and integration across multilateral environmental agreements facilitates consistent implementation across countries and levels (Claudet *et al.*, 2020).

In a globalizing world, governance functions are divided across countries, levels and actor groups. Producing countries may enact fundamental governance functions such as securing land ownership, monitoring or providing farmer support. However, these efforts are often undermined by powerful interest groups (Bebbington, 2015) and hence dependent on complementary institutional support from trading partners (Lenschow *et al.*, 2016). Instead of viewing producing countries as 'protector' of the environment, countries with high consumption can share part of the

responsibility for this environmental damage (Fuchs *et al.*, 2020; Zinngrebe *et al.*, 2024). Governmental interventions in consuming countries can reduce market pressure on producing countries by regulating demands, e.g., by regulating infrastructure, urban development or industrial policies (Cabernard & Pfister, 2022), or by advocating healthy and sustainable diets (Willett *et al.*, 2019) and fair trade. Effective solutions are enabled through collaborative partnerships providing complementary governance functions (Oberlack *et al.*, 2018; Ponte, 2019) and can be explicitly addressed in domestic biodiversity agendas in both producing and consuming countries (Cardona Santos *et al.*, 2023). Experiences show that despite general commitments to nature and sustainability, free-trade can lead to land-use change and biodiversity threats (Kehoe *et al.*, 2020; Mercado Cordova & Koo, 2023). Strengthening and specifying environmental safeguards, tracing the impacts with monitoring of trade and land-use, and strengthening legal responsibility and enforcement are central elements for sustainable trade agreements (Cesar de Oliveira *et al.*, 2024; Green *et al.*, 2019; Kehoe *et al.*, 2020).

5.6.4 Action 4.4: Strengthening learning through informed, accountable and adaptive governance based on diverse knowledge systems

Adaptive governance for transformation emphasizes the importance of participatory processes and accountability frameworks, which require far-reaching transformations of institutional structures (Ahern *et al.*, 2006; Arnold & Gunderson, 2013; Chaffin *et al.*, 2014; Christoplos *et al.*, 2009; Cosens *et al.*, 2021). Adopting new actor constellations and collaborations in creative learning processes can reframe problems and open new ways to overcome institutional path-dependency (Battilana *et al.*, 2009; Hoogstraaten *et al.*, 2020). Including a plurality of knowledge systems can help to navigate tensions, challenge established lock-ins and provide innovative solutions (Pascual *et al.*, 2021; Tengö *et al.*, 2014; Turnhout *et al.*, 2021) (see also target 21 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework on best available knowledge) (**Annex 5.2**). Positive coordination between administrative units is essential for fostering support and ensuring stakeholder involvement (Bagheri & Hjorth, 2007; Wamsler *et al.*, 2020). Flexible structures and institutional adjustments facilitate collaboration and address conflicts (Epstein *et al.*, 2015). Policy entrepreneurship and knowledge brokerage play pivotal roles in driving institutional change and cross-sectoral learning (Frantzeskaki *et al.*, 2012). Engagement promotes innovation and strengthens networks, bridging administrative groups and promoting nature considerations in policy agendas (Frisch Aviram *et al.*, 2020; Suarez *et al.*, 2023). For example, forming a broad coalition in a network

of actors including businesses, governments and knowledge institutions facilitated by the intermediaries has played a crucial role in promoting a circular economy in Amsterdam (Cramer, 2020).

Co-creating² knowledge in dominant knowledge systems depends on societal preconditions such as the representation of diverse perspectives, the capacity of integrative and transdisciplinary² research processes and norms to accommodate dissent and uncertainty (Bednarek *et al.*, 2018; Cornell *et al.*, 2013; Penca *et al.*, 2024). Co-creation of knowledge cultivated by a dynamic relationship among science, policy and society plays crucial a role in

shifting toward a sustainable society. This can be seen in the case of a rice paddy field system in Sado, Japan, where the collaborative learning process among farmers, researchers and governments identified high yield production systems in harmony with nature (Takahashi *et al.*, 2023). Knowledge integration is accomplished by overcoming system boundaries (boundary spanning), for instance across science and society (Bednarek *et al.*, 2018). Living Labs are one specific form to create vivid democratic spaces incorporating and creating scientific knowledge and political solutions (Almirall *et al.*, 2012; Hossain *et al.*, 2019; Van Geenhuizen, 2018).

Table 5.2 Examples reported in literature for implementing the four actions through National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans and related implementation processes.

Actions	Specific actions (prominent examples)	References
Action 4.1 – Strengthening biodiversity-related values in integrated governance across sectors	Shifting power relations ² and creating shared responsibilities through legal measures, integrating biodiversity with other topics and increasing public awareness of NBSAPs.	Coffey <i>et al.</i> (2023); Meyerhoff <i>et al.</i> (2012); Wüstemann <i>et al.</i> (2014).
	Inducing sectoral leadership to link sector strategies to NBSAPs and revise policies.	Alblas & van Zeven (2023); Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen <i>et al.</i> (2017); Pe'er <i>et al.</i> (2019); Whitehorn <i>et al.</i> (2019); Zinngrebe (2018, 2023).
	Conditioning governmental support and funding on compliance with NBSAP targets.	Prip <i>et al.</i> (2010); Sarkki <i>et al.</i> (2016).
Action 4.2 – Engaging diverse actors in inclusive governance to increase responsibility to act on biodiversity	Co-designing NBSAPs in intersectoral committees, coordination structures to induce responsibility and trust among sectors.	Apte (2007); Bulkeley <i>et al.</i> (2020); Göpfert <i>et al.</i> (2019); Prip & Pisupati (2018); Sarkki <i>et al.</i> (2016); Velázquez Gomar (2016); Whitehorn <i>et al.</i> (2019).
	Engaging civil society in thematic and Indigenous Peoples and local communities' events.	Baldauf (2020); Crowley <i>et al.</i> (2020).
	Establishing mediation processes to overcome intersectoral competition for resources.	Jiren <i>et al.</i> (2021); Sarvasova <i>et al.</i> (2013).
Action 4.3 – Securing collaboration and accountability through multilateral governance to address global interdependencies	Integrating multilateral environmental agreements by connecting topics, strategies, monitoring and processes.	Brörken <i>et al.</i> (2022); Prip, & Pisupati (2018); Redford <i>et al.</i> (2015); Roe <i>et al.</i> (2013); Sarkki <i>et al.</i> (2016); Velázquez Gomar, (2016).
	Addressing domestic consumption with external biodiversity effects in NBSAPs.	Friedman <i>et al.</i> (2018); Henders <i>et al.</i> (2018); Hugé, de Bisthoven, <i>et al.</i> (2020).
	Using the Convention on Biological Diversity voluntary peer review as a mechanism to improve NBSAPs.	Koh <i>et al.</i> (2022); A. Ulloa (2017).
Action 4.4 – Strengthening learning through accountable, informed and adaptive governance based on diverse knowledge systems	Co-evaluating NBSAPs and related policies and finance flows with key stakeholders (e.g., cross-sectoral reviews).	Sotirov & Storch (2018); Velázquez Gomar (2016).
	Establishing transparency and information disclosure for governments, business and others.	Brörken <i>et al.</i> (2022); Redford <i>et al.</i> (2015); Roe <i>et al.</i> (2013).
	Strengthening science-policy interaction in formalized fora and NBSAP evaluation processes.	Brörken <i>et al.</i> (2022); Redford <i>et al.</i> (2015); Roe <i>et al.</i> (2013).
	Assigning clear legal responsibilities combining hard and soft law.	Zinngrebe (2023).

5.7 STRATEGY 5: SHIFTING SOCIETAL VIEWS AND VALUES TO RECOGNIZE AND PRIORITIZE FUNDAMENTAL INTERCONNECTIONS BETWEEN HUMANS AND NATURE

Strategy 5 aims to address the root causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, including people's disconnection from nature and historical and contemporary relations of domination, power and wealth concentration and a short-term orientation (Quijano, 2000; Richardson *et al.*, 2020) (**Chapters 1 and 4**). Centering on five actions that have the potential to catalyse profound socio-cultural and transformative change (**Figure 5.12**), this strategy prioritizes the recognition of interconnections between humans and nature, leading to fundamental changes in collective thinking

and action regarding biodiversity and sustainability (Wamsler *et al.*, 2021; S. West *et al.*, 2021). The strategy promotes norms and values that shape biodiversity-related policies, emphasizing the interplay between beliefs, policies and technologies (Adger *et al.*, 2013; Ives *et al.*, 2020; Osberg *et al.*, 2024; Richardson *et al.*, 2020; Wamsler *et al.*, 2018, 2020). It emphasizes systemic reorganization driven by shifts in views and values across social, economic, environmental and technological spheres (IPBES, 2019). Building on the IPBES Values Assessment (IPBES, 2022a), it explores actions for shifting societal goals and norms, such as transitioning from relations of domination to relations of care, thereby enhancing well-being and interdependencies in the web of life (Ives *et al.*, 2023; Latour, 2005; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017; Richardson *et al.*, 2020) (**Chapters 1 and 4**). This involves embracing a multiplicity of worldviews and cultural perspectives, known as 'pluriversal living' (Escobar, 2018) and fostering reciprocal, care-oriented and non-exploitative relationships with nature and people (IPBES, 2022a; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017). It also involves promoting reciprocal human-nature relations (Foggin *et al.*, 2021; Ives *et al.*, 2018;

Figure 5.12 Addressing the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline by shifting individual and societal views and values.

The figure depicts the iterative, political and emergent process of transformative change through a spiral and arrow design, with a circle representing the co-creation of change in human-world relationships with self, others and the world at large. These are needed for a transformative change process that is equitable, care-oriented and just and can be nurtured by the five actions described in this section. This figure draws upon the research of the following, amongst others: Quijano (2000) on relations of domination; Escobar (2011, 2020) and Maldonado Torres (2016) on pluriversality; Haraway (2016), Plumwood (1993) and Puig de la Bellacasa (2017) on relations of care; Wamsler *et al.* (2021) on inner transformations; various authors cited in the assessment on the proposed strategies.

Krenak & Nunes, 2020; Plumwood, 2002) by recognizing the agency² and labour of plants and animals and their role as spiritual beings and kin, as in many Indigenous philosophies (Abbott, 2021; Barrett *et al.*, 2017; Country *et al.*, 2016).

5.7.1 Action 5.1: Increasing nature connectedness and recognition of human-nature interdependencies in complex webs of life

Disconnection from nature is a key underlying cause of biodiversity loss and nature's decline (Kellert, 2005). In parallel, biodiversity loss is associated with loss of cultural diversity and erosion of the social fabric (Ladle *et al.*, 2023). Nature connectedness acts as a catalyst for transformative change by fostering a deep sense of care and responsibility for the natural world. This emotional bond motivates individuals to adopt pro-environmental behaviours and to advocate for policies that prioritize biodiversity conservation and sustainable practices (Abson *et al.*, 2017; Mackay *et al.*, 2021). The benefits of nature connectedness extend beyond environmental impact; 'cross-worlding'² (Clark, 2024) also significantly enhances human wellbeing and resilience, highlighting the interdependencies between human and planetary wellbeing (Pritchard *et al.*, 2020). However, current efforts to foster nature connection often focus solely on providing green spaces, which alone are insufficient for promoting the deep, active and regular engagement necessary for transformative changes in the human-nature relationship that foster conservation values and behaviours (Richardson *et al.*, 2020). Activities that enhance appreciation for biodiversity and the interconnectedness of living organisms

are crucial for inducing sustainable behavioural and structural changes (IPBES, 2019). These activities include, for example, community engagement in environmental education, experiential learning opportunities and contemplative art practice (Flowers *et al.*, 2014). By drawing upon the relational philosophies associated with many Indigenous and local knowledge systems (Figure 5.13; Table 5.3; Figure 5.14) and providing opportunities to live 'as nature' (IPBES, 2022a), such activities can enhance learning and unite both human and nature's well-being (Kimmerer, 2013). There are actionable options to foster nature connectedness across the public realm from urban planning (*Green Minds Initiative*⁸) to healthcare (Wamsler *et al.*, 2024; Wamsler, Osberg, *et al.*, 2022) to child raising, e.g., "restoring humanity's evolved nest" (Narvaez & Bradshaw, 2023). Research shows that childhood experiences in nature generate both action for nature and feelings of connectedness with nature at later ages (Van Heel *et al.*, 2023; Van Heel *et al.*, 2023, 2024). Formal and informal education can promote human-nature connectedness (Pöllänen *et al.*, 2023; SEI & CEEW, 2022) and an ethics of care² (Plumwood, 2015) especially where it supports recognition of interdependencies, sensory and emotional connections, spiritualities and distributed agencies in entangled webs of life between humans, plants and animals (Latour, 2005; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017; West *et al.*, 2019; Whatmore, 2002). Formal education aimed at ecoliteracy also fosters critical thinking, reflexivity², and the capacity to challenge dominant narratives² and adopt pluralistic worldviews, essential for transformative change (Mezirow, 2000; Sterling, 2011).

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Table 5.3 Ways of characterizing human-nature relationships in diverse cultures and languages.

Many Indigenous and other relational philosophies recognize humans and nature as being deeply entangled, with an emphasis on care, reciprocity² and harmony. Creating space for plural understandings of reality and relating to nature based on ethics of care is important for transformative change for a just and sustainable world.

Examples	Origin	Source
Ahimsā² Principle of non-violence in the context of a cosmology where 'all lives are integrated and to harm others is to hurt the community as a whole'.	India	Singh (2014)
Birgejumpi² A North-Sámi concept that means to have a good life according to what one has access to, living in a modest way with interactions between humans and non-humans based on care and respect.	Sami	Rybråten <i>et al.</i> (2024)
Gaga² The Tayal Law' – a broad concept that encompasses ways of being and interacting with others and the land.	Tayal, Taiwa	Silan <i>et al.</i> (2022); Silan & Munkejord (2022)
Hurai² Translated as 'all the best things', it expresses the logic of transforming from nature to animals and then to human beings, in accord with Chinese Tuvan's people's cosmology. It sustains the belief that human beings are capable of continuously receiving the Hurai and blessing from nature.	Tuva, Siberia (China, Mongolia, Russia)	Hou (2019)

Table 5.3

Examples	Origin	Source
Kametsa asaike ² 'Living well together in this place' or 'Knowing the world as a network of mutually constituted human and other-than-human actors'	Ashaninka, Peruvian Amazon	Caruso & Sarmiento Barletti (2019)
Kawsak Sacha ² 'The living forest', a conscious living being who is the subject of rights and is inhabited by Runayuk, beings that protect ecosystems, animal and plant species.	Kichwa, Ecuador	IPBES (2022a); Pueblo Originario Kichwa de Sarayaku (2018)
Lekil kuxlejal ² In the Mayan language Tzeltal, the most similar word is islekil kuxlejal, which means 'good life', that is, what is done in order to integrate material, spiritual and communal needs.	Maya, Chiapas, Mexico	Ávila (2011) Paoli (2003)
Mino-mnaamodzawin ² The value of 'respect for the spirit in all things is rooted in Indigenous legal orders'.	Anishinaabek, United States of America	IPBES (2022a) (see Chapter 2)
Mino-bimaatisiwin ² 'Living a good life/balanced life is a basic principle (...) which informs a set of principles and protocols in human actions that are manifested not only in offerings, reverence, non-greed and non-waste, but are used to make decisions affecting community landscapes.' 'Minobimaatisiwin is embedded within a holistic world view and thus involves living in respectful and reciprocal terms with all of Creation at individual and collective levels.' 'Reciprocal relations are required not only among people, but with all other 'relatives' as well – animals; plants; rocks; water; spirits; celestial beings such as the moon, sun and stars; ancestors; and those yet to come.'	Anishinaabe United States of America	Borrows (2016); IPBES, (2022a, p. 59); LaDuke (1994); McGregor (2018)
Nanao ñu'u ² 'Means to rediscover human-nature bonds and reconnect with values of equity, respect and care with nanao ñu'u (our mother), in the Tu'un Javi language which recognizes seven types /names for rain'.	Mixtec, Mexico	IPBES (2022a, p. 59)
Saffu ² 'This principle guides people's lives and impels them to respect and do justice to one's own ayyaana (spirit) and that of other beings'.	Oromo, Ethiopia	IPBES (2022a); Kelbessa (2005)
Sumak Kawsay and Suma Qamaña ² Indigenous Andean worldviews in South America that 'conceptualize a good quality of life through broad values that guide human-human and human-nature interconnections.' 'A linguistic analysis shows that the conceptual root of <i>suma qamaña</i> (<i>buen vivir</i> or living well) is convivial gathering or community in which basic needs are met and relationships, which even extend to the Earth, are harmonious. Living well implies a strong ethical component of valuing and appreciating the distinctiveness of others, as well as spirituality ² or lifestyle and so can never be just economic. <i>Suma qamaña</i> is 'broader than well-being, emphasizing the importance of harmonious relations between nature and human beings and providing an important link to sustainability that current conceptions of well-being fail to make.'	Kichwa & Aymara, South America Aymara, Bolivia	Albó (2018); IPBES (2022a) Albó (2018)
Satoyama, Satoumi, Fūdo ² 'The entwined relations between people-and-nature and people-and-people' expressed through living in nature exist in myriad ways, e.g., in the Japanese concepts, reflecting dynamic relationships between people, habitats and species.	Japan	IPBES (2022a, p. 71); Takeuchi <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Ubuntu ² 'In sub-Saharan Africa, the relational values system of the Ubuntu philosophy focuses on reciprocity, dialogue and collective humanity, which are extended to nature and have been applied in development, external relations, educational and health practices.'	Sub-Saharan Africa	Chibvongodze (2016); Eze (2019); Le Grange, (2012); Lefa (2015); Qobo & Nyathi (2016)
Whakapapa ² Refers to cultural connectedness for the Indigenous Māori that encompasses both ancestry and nature and determines the relationships and obligations that exist for them living within the natural world rather than separate from it (e.g., <i>Ko au te awa, ko te awa ko au</i> is a Māori saying that translates to 'I am the river and the river is me'). Whakapapa is the act of reciting in proper order layers or generations of knowledge. It recognizes the origin of mankind from <i>Papatūānuku</i> (the Earth Mother) and <i>Ranginui</i> (Sky Father) and the intertwining of relationships across all of nature since man's conception (Figure 5.14).	Maori, New Zealand	Charpleix (2018); Mahuika (2019); Ngata & Ngata (2019); Roskrug (2007)
Warinyi ² 'Among the speakers of the Warumungu language in Australia habitat-based classification is expressed through the suffix <i>warinyi</i> . This designation has implications for interactions and relationships between humans and other-than-human beings, since, according to this worldview, all "dwellers" of a particular habitat (e.g., plants, animals, humans, etc.) have equal rights.'		IPBES (2022a, p. 55)

Figure 5.14 **Te Ira Tangata (The life principle of man).**

Artwork by Makuini Te Whata-Chadwick in 2003 and kindly provided by Nicholas Roskrige – CC BY 4.0. This artwork depicts the Te Ao Maori creation of the world in which humankind celebrates the relationship that moved Maori peoples' whakapapa from the spiritual to the physical world to parent humankind.

5.7.2 Action 5.2: Shifting culture through new narratives

Addressing the challenge of biodiversity loss and nature's decline can be achieved through a transformation of cultural relationships between humans and non-humans, through shared narratives and imaginaries that shape these interactions (Huntjens & Kemp, 2022; Kimmerer, 2013; Richardson *et al.*, 2020; Riedy, 2020). Shared narratives, paradigms² and imaginaries reflect how humans collectively understand identities and relations to others and nature (Castoriadis, 1997) and the values that are prioritized, which may be more or less sustainable (Pascual *et al.*, 2023). This action involves shifting away from anthropocentric narratives that frame nature as separate from, and to be controlled and exploited by people. It makes way for pluriversal imaginaries (Escobar, 2018) that celebrate human-nature interdependencies and reciprocities and recognize the agency and rights of

non-human life to flourish⁹ (Gudynas, 2011). It promotes an ethics of care and regeneration (Haraway, 2016; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017) and amplifies more diversified values associated with collective societal wellbeing (Harmáčková *et al.*, 2023; **Figure 5.13**). Cultural initiatives like music, storytelling, theatre, films and festivals as well as transformative journalism advocating for sustainability and social justice² (Brüggemann *et al.*, 2021) play a critical role in driving this shift by offering new paradigms and perspectives on humans' relationship with nature. These cultural modes of narrating human-nature relations increase accessibility to experiences with affective power. Language, concepts and practices reflecting interdependencies with nature or ways of 'living as nature' based on ethics of care, are central to dynamic Indigenous and relational philosophies. The defence

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and revitalization actions to sustain such cultures and promote wider learning beyond Indigenous contexts are key to sustainability transformations, including Indigenous approaches like Sumak Kawsay, Ubuntu or Whakapapa (**Table 5.3; Figure 5.14**) all of which emphasize reciprocity and care (Calderón *et al.*, 2018) and which have been sidelined by relations of domination (**Chapter 4**).

Many Indigenous and local knowledge systems and narratives already have these characteristics and can guide cultural change (IPBES, 2023; Kimmerer, 2013; LaDuke, 1999; McGregor *et al.*, 2023; Reed *et al.*, 2024; Topa & Narvaez, 2022). For example, when the worldviews of Indigenous Peoples and local communities guide conservation governance and management, as in the case of Ecuador incorporating the rights of Pachamama into its Constitution (Constitucion de la Republica del Ecuador, 2008), there is greater conservation effectiveness and more equitable social outcomes (Dawson, Coolsaet, *et al.*, 2021; Martín-López *et al.*, 2020) (see also **Strategy 1**). Adoption of the Universal Declaration for the Rights of Mother Earth (2010) by Bolivia and other entities around the world contributes to a shift in cultural narratives and norms about the links between human and nature's well-being. The knowledge, practices and worldviews of Indigenous Peoples and local communities can also guide sustainable use of wild species. Conversely, the loss of Indigenous and local languages, along with insufficient attention to gendered roles, including those in matrilineal and matriarchal cultures, poses a threat to this sustainable use (IPBES, 2022b). As Bate (2005) observes, "if you want to change the way people think, you should change the way they talk."

Complementing and affirming Indigenous worldviews, a new paradigm based on scientific breakthroughs is revealing a radically expanded perception of the world and realizing the unitive nature of reality; this view, based in science, is convergent with universal wisdom teachings (Currivan, 2022; Currivan & Laszlo, 2017). Adoption of this unitive worldview and narrative, and the inclusive values and ethical principles they nurture, would constitute cultural expressions of this view, and could be empowered through art, dialogue and collaborative re-imagining of educational opportunities, embedding the concept of unity in interdependent diversity.

Exploitative narratives can be challenged through political action and participatory deliberation that exposes injustice and gives voice and representation to humans and non-humans (de la Cadena & Blaser, 2018; Escobar, 2020; Whyte, 2020). Education can give active voice to nature and shift narratives beyond human exceptionalism (Plumwood, 1993). Storytelling, visioning², audiovisual arts, festivals and participatory creative practices play a critical role by offering new perspectives on humans' relationship

with nature and by fostering imagination, sense-making and emotional engagement with environmental issues (Galafassi *et al.*, 2018; Niigaaniin & MacNeill, 2022; Riedy, 2022; Vervoort *et al.*, 2024; Yudkin *et al.*, 2022). It is important that these narratives are communicated across various platforms (e.g., biodiversity champions) and through different organizations (e.g., schools, religious organizations, charities or civic society groups) to engage citizens from different communities.

5.7.3 Action 5.3: Changing social norms regarding production and consumption

By strategically enhancing the visibility of desired behaviours and deploying targeted policy measures, it is possible to catalyze and sustain new social norms (Constantino *et al.*, 2022; Schneider & Van Der Linden, 2023). Understanding the mechanisms behind the spread of new social norms, ideas and behaviours is crucial for designing effective strategies that encourage societal transformation. The propagation of new social norms, ideas or behaviours often occurs through complex processes within social networks, starting slowly until a critical mass of early adopters is reached (Becken *et al.*, 2021; Fink *et al.*, 2021; Lehmann & Ahn, 2018). This process is influenced by the degree of similarity among interacting individuals, the alignment of new norms with existing values and the practicality of the behaviours being promoted (Kaaronen & Strelkovskii, 2020; Lehmann & Ahn, 2018; Nyborg *et al.*, 2016; Schaumberg & Skowronek, 2022; Séré De Lanauze & Siadou-Martin, 2019; Woody, 2015). As transitioning to new behaviours often involves significant costs, supportive policies such as taxes, fees, subsidies or infrastructure investments are essential (Nyborg *et al.*, 2016; Stiglitz *et al.*, 2017). This approach underscores the importance of integrating social dynamics with policy interventions to facilitate transformative changes within communities, ultimately fostering more sustainable and adaptive social systems (Fesenfeld, 2022; Pahle *et al.*, 2018).

Social norms, which define acceptable behaviour, can shift rapidly, leading to widespread changes in behaviour by denormalizing certain practices while normalizing others (Abson *et al.*, 2017; Nyborg *et al.*, 2016). These changes, driven by diverse actors including policymakers, activists and community leaders, create social license and enforce structural changes (de Haan & Rotmans, 2018; Naito *et al.*, 2022). Targeted actors in the realm of production and consumption include producers, consumers, processors, importers, retailers, investors, financial institutions and governments (Harris, 2023). Policies, laws and regulations including rights-based approaches, play a critical role (Atuo *et al.*, 2020; Tauli-Corpuz *et al.*, 2020). To encourage key actors to choose sustainable consumption options,

policy-makers may use taxes, subsidies, bans or quotas and controls on advertising (Harris, 2023). Educational initiatives and awareness campaigns are crucial for promoting behaviour change by making sustainable choices more attractive (Grune-Yanoff & Hertwig, 2016; Kaaronen & Strelkovskii, 2020; Wamsler & Osberg, 2022) and making sustainable information accessible (Deselnicu *et al.*, 2014; M. Harris, 2023; Upham *et al.*, 2011). Campaigning, protest and civil disobedience through social movements² can initiate significant norm changes, particularly when supported by robust social networks (**Strategy 2**). However, the spread of misinformation or disinformation among the public by social networks and social media (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017; Del Vicario *et al.*, 2016; Pennycook & Rand, 2019; Stewart *et al.*, 2019) and/or science (J. D. West & Bergstrom, 2021) may pose a challenge to transformative change.

Telecoupling² in trade, a result of globalization, is increasingly problematic for biodiversity (**Chapter 4**). For example, in food systems, telecoupling involves growing disconnections between producers and consumers and hides the impacts of consumption, such as land use change, deforestation and biodiversity losses. Overcoming the negative effects of telecoupling might be accomplished through deeper shifts in values (Santika *et al.*, 2024), moderating market values and amplifying care and solidarity (IPBES, 2022a; Santika *et al.*, 2024).

Research on non-violent social movements, organizational change and shifting opinions, beliefs, social norms and conventions suggests that anywhere from 3.5% to 25% of the population can drive significant societal shifts (Centola *et al.*, 2018; Chenoweth & Stephan, 2012; Kotter, 2012; Xie *et al.*, 2011). An example of changing social norms is the increasing use of reusable shopping bags over single-use plastic bags, driven by environmental campaigns, regulatory changes and public awareness (Clapp & Swanston, 2009; Sharp *et al.*, 2010). However, social norm changes around consumption can be hindered by pervasive relations of domination and broader macro-economic systemic issues, such as the limited access to sustainable food options in food deserts, as described in **Chapter 4**.

5.7.4 Action 5.4: Facilitating transformative learning processes and spaces that foster nature-inclusive thinking and acting

Transformative learning² utilizes action-oriented teaching strategies, such as dialogue and experiential activities, to cultivate essential inner capacities in individuals of all ages. These inner capacities encompass a range of cognitive, emotional and relational skills and qualities that enable individuals to develop new understandings, engage

in critical reflection and ultimately drive transformative change (Mezirow, 1997, 2009; Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2008; Wamsler *et al.*, 2020). Examples of such capacities include systems thinking², empathy, self-awareness and the ability to envision and create alternative futures. By fostering these inner capacities, transformative learning empowers individuals to shift deeply rooted perspectives and values (Harmáčková *et al.*, 2023; IPBES, 2022a), change behaviours and actively address the global environmental challenges and crises, including climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution (Bawa *et al.*, 2007; Dawson, Coolsaet, *et al.*, 2021; Fraude *et al.*, 2021; Wamsler *et al.*, 2020). Transformative learning connects the inner development of cognitive, social and emotional changes to ethical, place-sensitive, trauma-informed and creative understandings (Singer-Brodowski, 2023; Sterling, 2011). This nurtures relational being, thinking and acting (Cooper & Gibson, 2022; Wamsler *et al.*, 2021). Fostering agency for transformative change also involves facilitating dialogues that build trust and explore different perspectives, values and norms, rather than simply winning arguments (Aarts, 2023; Leeuwis & Aarts, 2021). These spaces should include diverse participants to ensure a wide range of perspectives and knowledge are represented (Sterling *et al.*, 2018). Learnings are harvested through reflective practices (Wals & Corcoran, 2012) and are then integrated into strategic decisions, enhancing the core elements of transformative change (Aarts, 2023; Lotz-Sisitka *et al.*, 2015; Sterling *et al.*, 2018; Wals & Corcoran, 2012). Widespread engagement in transformative learning can mainstream inner dimensions of development into practices and structures, facilitating broad cultural shifts, as is the aim of initiatives such as the Inner Development Goals, The Inner Green Deal and the UNDP Conscious Food Systems Alliance (Inner Development Goals, 2021; Jordan, 2021; Wamsler *et al.*, 2023; Wamsler, Bristow, *et al.*, 2022). Transformative learning fosters learning communities within ‘solution spaces’ which are collaborative environments designed to address the systemic issues driving biodiversity loss and nature’s decline. These communities enable creative envisioning of positive futures through ‘imagination infrastructures’ (Hopkins, 2019; Mulgan, 2022). By building trust, inclusive community identity and shared wisdom, such spaces inspire resilient, equitable, just and sustainable futures (A. a Fischer *et al.*, 2014; Moser, 2013; Pisters *et al.*, 2019; Yudkin *et al.*, 2022; Zygmunt *et al.*, 2018). For example, research in sustainable production of coffee and, in establishing a circular economy more broadly, has found transformation in mindsets and values towards sustainable supply chains is supported through collective learning, across individuals, sectors and the broader systems (Hochachka, 2021; Hofstetter *et al.*, 2021).

5.7.5 Action 5.5: Co-creating knowledge and weaving diverse knowledge systems

Knowledge co-creation and giving validity to plural forms of knowledge is crucial for developing actionable and inclusive biodiversity and sustainability strategies (Ives *et al.*, 2023; Miller & Wyborn, 2020; Wyborn, 2015). This involves decolonising academia and making space for Indigenous and local knowledge, as well as social sciences, arts and humanities, as well as public engagement (Wijngaarden & Ole Murero, 2023). A broader approach to research methodologies is needed to increase understanding of the root causes that reinforce the status quo, including the many explicit and implicit forms of power that narrow public imagination and debate over alternatives (Barrett, 2011; Castree, 2015; Fisher, 2009; Stoddard *et al.*, 2021; Wamsler & Riggers, 2018; Woroniecki *et al.*, 2019) (**Chapters 2 and 4**). Co-creating knowledge can enhance biodiversity management by weaving Indigenous, local and scientific knowledge systems and ensuring that strategies that integrate inner and outer dimensions of transformation are culturally appropriate, scientifically robust and ecologically viable (Ives *et al.*, 2023; Miller & Wyborn, 2020; Petzold *et al.*, 2020; Smith *et al.*, 2022; K. P. Whyte, 2017). Co-creation principles such as equity, respect, recognition and collaboration emphasize inclusivity and prioritize the needs of marginalized groups, facilitating transformative interventions (Chambers *et al.*, 2022; Mauser *et al.*, 2013; Miller & Wyborn, 2020; Norström *et al.*, 2020). A review of empirical studies shows that knowledge co-creation results in diverse outcomes, from improved processes (e.g., power redistribution, reflexivity) to proximate outcomes (e.g., expanded knowledge base, increased capacities) or intervention outcomes (e.g., well-being and product improvement, changes in knowledge systems) (Wyborn *et al.*, 2019). Examples include increased adaptive capacity² in Arctic communities (Alessa *et al.*, 2016), disaster preparedness of communities in Nepal, and the establishment of adaptive management of climate change monitoring in a rural community in Tanzania (Shaffer *et al.*, 2022).

Recent research includes arguments for the use of intuitive interspecies communication to facilitate inclusion of more-than-human knowledge in conservation decision-making (Abbott, 2021; Barrett *et al.*, 2021; Wijngaarden, 2023). Co-creation also serves as an essential pillar for counteracting disinformation that is harmful for biodiversity and the environment, since different knowledge holders and practitioners, together with scientists, are needed to enable political mechanisms and legal actions, and to devise strategies connected to science and media literacy. All of these contribute to effectively tackling disinformation (Farrell *et al.*, 2019; Lazer *et al.*, 2018). Action-oriented co-creation involves various stakeholders in participatory action research and transdisciplinary methods that address societal

challenges, producing socially robust knowledge (Chambers *et al.*, 2022; Schubotz, 2020; Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020). These processes can be enhanced with capacity-building among all participants to ensure readiness for collective, ongoing partnerships (West *et al.*, 2021). Key individuals whose expertise cuts across epistemologies may play an important role in facilitating or leading this co-creation (Hatch *et al.*, 2023). The generation of knowledge for sustainability should directly address relations of domination forged in the colonial era and now pervasive in modern societies (Arora & Stirling, 2023) (**Chapter 4**) with efforts to co-create sustainable futures based on relations of care for flourishing life.

Several specific policy instruments² based on the principles of consent, intellectual and cultural autonomy and justice exist, or have been proposed to support and provide accountability to principles of knowledge co-creation and accountability (Kasdan *et al.*, 2021; Orlove *et al.*, 2023) (Action 5.5 in Annex 5.6). These instruments mostly focus on knowledge co-creation with Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and include full consultation, free, prior and informed consent, recognition of customary law, intellectual property rights, Indigenous data sovereignty, and capacity-building for use of technology (Godden & Tehan, 2016; Lusiru & Malekela, 2022; Reeves *et al.*, 2022; Tormos-Aponte, 2021) (Action 5.5 in Annex 5.6). While these instruments are not a panacea, their absence makes knowledge co-creation unlikely if not impossible. The expansion of their use and their full implementation has powerful transformative potential (Annex 5.6).

5.8 PATHWAYS LINKING STRATEGIES, ACTIONS AND OUTCOMES

The five strategies and 22 actions presented differ in the way they engage with views, structures and practices. Depending on the contextual preconditions and societal dynamics, the selection and combination of actions from different strategies allows one to construct purposive pathways, from short-term to long-term action, leading to broader and sustained transformation (Ferguson *et al.*, 2013; Wise *et al.*, 2014). Overall, the actions described above can be strategically combined in complementary and synergistic ways to address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline (**Chapter 1**) via transformative pathways leading to a plurality of visions aligned with global sustainability and the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity (**Chapter 2**). Pathways are comprised of specific steps and processes for achieving outcomes aligned with these visions. The diverse approaches to transformative change (**Chapter 3**) inform an equally diverse set of pathways for

achieving those visions (Leach *et al.*, 2010; Scoones *et al.*, 2015). Transformative pathways inevitably include challenges (**Chapter 4**) which must be strategically navigated. Co-developing pathways with the central actors across sectors and scales enables reframing problems to overcome lock-ins and contextualization (Nóbrega *et al.*, 2023). Articulating aspirational pathways to diverse visions can be a creative exercise using the arts to surface diverse perspectives from multiple knowledge systems and their associated aspirations for human-nature relationships (Pereira *et al.*, 2023).

For example, the challenges associated with operationalizing the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

exemplify the challenge of operationalizing transformative change. **Table 5.4** identifies such challenges and which of the actions described in this chapter can help achieve the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework targets.²

To further highlight how the pathways concept can be used to guide decision-making and adapt to changing circumstances while navigating towards visions and transformed futures, the remainder of this section includes two hypothetical examples of integrated fiscal, legal and governance interventions and a real-world example of transformative change in food systems associated with agroecology.

Table 5.4 Actions for achieving the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

The table lists a subset of targets aiming at “tools and solutions for implementation and mainstreaming”. For each target, the table presents key challenges (**Chapter 4**), key actions and specific options for its implementation (**Chapter 5**).

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework	Key implementation challenges	Relevant actions	Specific options for action implementation
Target 14 Integrate biodiversity in decision-making at every level	#3 Inadequate policies and unfit institutions	Action 4.1 Strengthening biodiversity in integrated governance Action 4.4 Strengthening learning through informed, accountable and adaptive governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing legal accountability to biodiversity targets Increasing transparency and evaluation Developing collaborative processes for co-designing, co-monitoring and co-evaluating policies Conditioning governmental budgets (and business investments) on biodiversity performance Supporting and incentivizing administrative entrepreneurship mandates and incentives
Target 15 Businesses assess, disclose and reduce biodiversity-related risks and negative impacts	#4 Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices	Action 3.3 Reforming financial systems Action 3.4 Adopting metrics of success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adopting metrics of success that account for nature and equity Natural capital accounting e.g., SEEA/EA prioritizing biodiversity Disclosing impacts and dependencies on nature, as well as response plans in corporate reporting Building capacities for monitoring and adaptive learning Reducing elite capture and lobbying. Distributing benefits evenly
Target 16 Enable sustainable consumption choices to reduce waste and overconsumption	#4 Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices	Action 3.3 Reforming financial systems Action 2.1 regulating direct exploitation of organisms Action 5.3 Changing social norms regarding production and consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Declining caps on resource use Sufficiency policies Supporting “non-for profit” initiatives Supporting local consumption Regulating consumptive behaviour
Target 17 Strengthen biosafety and distribute the benefits of biotechnology	#5 Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems ²	Action 2.2 Embedding technology in transformative frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoiding path-dependencies induced by genetic modification Regulating monopolies resulting from technology packages Assuring legal rights for non-users and benefit sharing Co-developing requirements for technologies in a participatory way Promoting open-source and open-access technology Promoting technologies to overcome resource dependencies

Table 5.4

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework	Key implementation challenges	Relevant actions	Specific options for action implementation
<p>Target 18 Reduce harmful incentives by at least \$500 billion per year and scale up positive incentives for biodiversity</p>	<p>#2 Economic and political inequalities #3 Inadequate policies and unfit institutions</p>	<p>Action 3.3 Reforming financial systems Action 2.3 Financing for global sustainability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reforming subsidies in productive sectors Implementing redistributive policies Assuring policy coherence, global coordinated action and contextualisation Monitoring and evaluation are key levers for meaningful reforms to safeguard nature
<p>Target 19 Mobilize \$200 billion per year for biodiversity from all sources, including \$30 billion through international finance</p>	<p>#1 Persistent relations of domination #2 Economic and political inequalities</p>	<p>Action 3.3 Reforming financial systems Action 2.3 Financing for global sustainability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using biodiversity requirements to redirect existing national and international financial flows (e.g., REDD+, EU Agri-Env. schemes, UK ELMS) and private investments Removing harmful subsidies for productive sectors to mobilize funds (~\$10 trillion per year) Using debt relief for poorest countries to provide budgets Restructuring development aid (including support for productivity and social targets such as anti-drug campaigns)
<p>Target 20 strengthen capacity-building, technology transfer² and scientific and technical cooperation for biodiversity</p>	<p>#5 Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems</p>	<p>Action 4.4 Strengthening learning through informed, accountable and adaptive governance Action 5.4 Facilitating transformative learning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considering social aspects of innovation to avoid purely technological approaches that can lead to inequality and compromise biodiversity Screening for context specific, Indigenous or local technologies Promoting transformative learning through experiential activities and reflection (e.g. through solution spaces, imagination infrastructure, action research)
<p>Target 21 Ensure that knowledge is available and accessible to guide biodiversity action</p>	<p>#5 Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation system</p>	<p>Action 5.4 Facilitating transformative learning Action 4.4 Strengthening learning through informed, accountable and adaptive governance</p>	<p>Transformative change goes beyond a 'provision' of knowledge by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing flexibility/ coordination of administrative units Creating networks and team building for entrepreneurship Integrating transdisciplinary processes (co-creation, living labs) Using boundary spanning to bridge knowledge systems Promoting transformative learning spaces in action-oriented processes Using arts and cultural expressions to stimulate imaginations, sense-making and emotional resilience for biophilic emotion Establishing interdisciplinary task forces Supporting community-led capacity-building initiatives
<p>Target 22 Ensure participation in decision-making and access to justice and information Related to biodiversity for all</p>	<p>#1 Persistent relations of domination #2 Economic and political inequalities</p>	<p>Action 4.2 Engaging diverse actors in inclusive governance Action 4.1 Strengthening biodiversity in integrated governance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creating visions and new social contracts Defining actor specific responsibilities in legal frameworks Assuring representation of biodiversity values in decision making Including plural voices to reflect knowledge systems and generate perceived responsibility
<p>Target 23 Ensure gender equality and a gender-responsive approach for biodiversity action</p>	<p>#1 Relations of Domination forged during the colonial era and pervasive modernities #2 Economic and political inequalities</p>	<p>Action 4.2 Engaging diverse actors in inclusive governance Action 4.1 Strengthening biodiversity in integrated governance</p>	<p>Implementing gender responsiveness in participatory processes indicated in target 22.</p>

5.8.1 Examples of transformative pathways

Illustrative examples of how the strategies outlined in **Chapter 5** are operationalized for two hypothetical examples through a set of actions for different strategies implemented by various actors over time to reach desired outcomes (**Figure 5.15**). Preconditions are outlined on the far left of the figure, which flows from left to right over time. Each pathway presents a set of actions associated with specific strategies and includes challenges that must be overcome. Intermediate outcomes and interventions made by certain actors lead to the ultimate outcomes associated with the desirable visions (**Figure 5.1**).

5.8.1.1 Example 1: Beyond economic valuation of nature

This hypothetical pathway draws from the rights of nature discourse (**Action 1.2**), implemented in various countries, including Bolivia, Ecuador, New Zealand and Spain which there provides legal protection to nature from harmful extractive activities (e.g., fossil fuels, overfishing, deforestation) (**Figure 5.15**). The first step along this pathway is a general institutionalization of nature's rights. In parallel, this pathway focuses on the application of innovative financial tools, starting with the integration of sustainability criteria into economic decisions and rules to incentivize companies towards best practices (**Action 3.1**). Activating these actions implies some preconditions to enable their implementation, including the recognition of Indigenous Peoples' views on nature (**Action 1.1**), political will of national governments, changing access criteria to loans by central banks (**Action 3.3**) and activism by stakeholders and shareholders for financial sector reform (**Action 3.3**). If preconditions are not in place, the first step is to establish them.

Implementing such actions would face challenges, e.g., pushback resulting from the difficulty of achieving consensus, limited institutionalization of proposals like the recognition of the 'rights of nature' when this opposes countries' legal frameworks, or opposition from extractive companies that might lobby against it. In such instances, citizen activism and in particular shareholder activism, can be a powerful tool to ensure reforms take place (**Action 2.4**). An interim outcome could be the recognition of rights of nature by the United Nations Environment Assembly (**Action 1.2**) and the reallocation of finance towards nature restoring activities (**Action 2.3**), which might eventually lead to a global increase in nature positive businesses (**Action 3.3**).

When successfully implemented, these actions might synergistically lead to a higher risk profile for nature-eroding companies and to the prosecution of extractive companies

for ecocide in the International Court of Justice. This might, in turn, lead to a direct reduction in harmful activities as companies become wary of prosecution (**Action 2.1**).

5.8.1.2 Example 2: Subsidies and conservation of the high seas

This hypothetical pathway focuses on intervention options for the marine environment. It starts with the reform of subsidies to economic sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature decline and the reallocation of financial resources towards improving marine conservation measures and the sustainability of small-scale fisheries (as was done for New Zealand fisheries) (Campling & Havice, 2013) (**Action 2.3; Figure 5.17**). Taking this action at the global level (Claudet *et al.*, 2020; Sumaila *et al.*, 2024) is likely to face direct push-back from groups currently benefiting from subsidy allocations.

The second action in this pathway seeks to make global institutions fit for global commons problems (**Action 4.3**). This could include closing some areas to large-scale commercial fisheries, as closing off high seas areas of spawning aggregations results in significant ecological benefits for migratory species (Sumaila *et al.*, 2015) (**Action 1.3**), since treating fisheries as common property in areas beyond the exclusive economic zones has led to overexploitation (Crespo *et al.*, 2019; Ortuño Crespo & Dunn, 2017). However, displacing fishing effort into domestic waters might impact local communities, so other governance mechanisms are needed to ensure that fishing in these areas is sustainable and equitable (Skerritt *et al.*, 2023). This would entail strengthening fisheries co-management systems for sustainability and social equity (**Action 4.2**), but also enforcement and compliance of national regulations and the need for rights-based management, wherein catches assigned to fishers and fleets are constrained (**Action 2.1**).

One sustainable fishing enabler would be to downscale consumption patterns through the increase of awareness about sustainable fisheries and consumption choices (e.g., increasing the offer of local products with low ecological footprint) (**Action 5.3**). Transparency and accountability of companies in consuming countries (**Action 4.3**) can lead to competitive advantages for companies in business reporting (**Action 3.4**) and product certification (**Action 2.1**), two important tools for fisheries sustainability. Product certification could be implemented within a system that ensures auditability and a thorough application of its principles, thereby enhancing current eco-labelling schemes (Christian *et al.*, 2013).

Combined, these three actions can lead to an overall structural shift that changes views, structures and practices, reduces the dominance of fisheries oriented towards

Figure 5 15 Two examples of transformative pathways.

The figure shows examples of transformative pathways considering different preconditions and the implementation of different strategies for transformation and potential outcomes that could derive from those alternative pathways. The figure shows the interplay of views, structures and practices as well as the role of strategies, options and barriers for transformation.

overextraction, reconfigures the power dynamics and promotes a shift of views, where economic growth is not the primary goal (**Action 3.4**). Across these actions, good governance, including transparency and effective monitoring and learning, is essential for enabling and sustaining transformative outcomes (**Action 4.4**).

5.8.2 Transformative change in practice: agroecological pathways

Many visions of transformative change relate to alternative ways of producing food and fibre. Of the 881 visions in the **Chapter 2** database¹⁰, 113 visions (13%) mention food. Many visions, such as those proposed by L'era and SOCLA (see Annex 5.7 for descriptions of these visions), reflect widespread agreement about the need for fundamental shifts across views, structures and practices in current food systems and recognize agroecology as playing a central role in transformative change.

Agroecology is a form of agricultural production that relies on biodiversity-mediated ecosystem services and nature's contributions to people and embodies holistic values encompassing ecological diversity, synergies, resilience and social values such as equity and dignity. Agroecological transitions offer an example of transformative change in food systems, redirecting unsustainable agricultural practices

towards biodiverse and equitable solutions addressing food security, poverty and biodiversity restoration, while recognizing the pivotal role of small-scale farmers and challenging dominant discourses on industrial agriculture (Bezner Kerr *et al.*, 2023; Gliessman & Titonell, 2015; Nicholls & Altieri, 2018; Wezel *et al.*, 2020). Some countries such as Mexico, France or Senegal have issued national laws, policies and programmes in support of agroecology, but the countries and regions where agroecology has expanded the most are those where strong social movements co-exist with such policies. For example, in Brazil (Teixeira *et al.*, 2018) pre-existing social movements supporting agroecology and the equitable access to land found conducive conditions created by national programmes such as *Fome Zero* or the National Law on Agroecological and Organic Production (van den Berg *et al.*, 2022). Examples worldwide showcase the efficacy of agroecology at enhancing climate resilience, recycling resources, promoting circularity, fostering community-based initiatives based on relational values and supporting local economies and social cohesion (**Table 5.5**). Increasing biodiversity, protecting native habitats, and reducing external inputs in agricultural landscapes has enhanced crop productivity by an average of 24% for a variety of crop systems worldwide (Garibaldi *et al.*, 2016).

Ongoing processes of agroecological transitions offer vital lessons for pathways of transformative change (**Figure 5.17**). Agroecology embodies the four principles of transformative change: i) equity and justice; ii) pluralism and inclusion; iii) respect for nature; and iv) adaptive learning

10. Visions database analysis strategy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242913>).

Table 5.5 **Examples of social and ecological processes relevant to biodiversity conservation enhanced through agroecological transitions.**

Enhanced process	Examples	Illustrative references
Climate resilience	<p>Following Hurricane Mitch in Central America in 1998, farms practicing agroecology (e.g., agroforestry, contour farming, cover cropping) retained 20 to 40% more topsoil, suffered less erosion and experienced lower economic losses than neighbouring farms practicing conventional monocultures.</p> <p>Pastoralist households of North Patagonia exhibited greater resilience to 10 years of frequent droughts and a faster recovery from a massive volcanic ashfall in 2011, when they were able to diversify, relying on local and adapted landraces and knowledge and when household decisions were shared between male and female pastoralists.</p>	<p>Febles & Félix (2020); Holt-Giménez (2002); Laborda <i>et al.</i> (2024); Reising <i>et al.</i> (2022)</p>
Recycling and pest regulation	<p>In Asia, integrated rice systems combine rice cultivation with the generation of other products such as fish, ducks and trees. Rice and fish form a symbiosis: The rice provides the fish with shelter and shade and a reduced water temperature, along with herbivorous insects and other small animals that feed on the rice. Rice benefits from nitrogenous waste from the fish, while the fish reduce insect pests such as brown planthoppers and diseases such as sheath blight of rice and weeds.</p> <p>Push-pull cropping systems in East Africa combine species that repel insect pests and attract their natural enemies through volatile semio-chemicals; such combination of species (e.g., cereals, legumes and grasses) may provide other contributions, such as fodder production, biological nitrogen fixation and erosion control.</p>	<p>Brouwer <i>et al.</i> (2015); Kebede <i>et al.</i> (2018); Khumairoh <i>et al.</i> (2021); J. Xie <i>et al.</i> (2011)</p>

Table 5 5

Enhanced process	Examples	Illustrative references
Synergies through diversification	<p>Agroforestry systems that include deep rooting trees can capture nutrients lost beyond the roots of annual crops, improve the soil water balance for crops and grasslands and improve animal welfare.</p> <p>Globally, biological nitrogen fixation by pulses in intercropping systems or rotations generates about \$10 million savings in nitrogen fertilizers every year while contributing to soil health, climate change mitigation and adaptation².</p> <p>Countries with larger crop diversity also support more agricultural employment.</p>	<p>Billen <i>et al.</i>, (2021); Buratti-Donham <i>et al.</i> (2023); FAO (2016); Garibaldi & Pérez-Méndez (2019); Teixeira <i>et al.</i>, (2018)</p>
Circularity through crop-livestock integration	<p>Nutrient cycling accounts for 51% of the economic value of all non-provisioning nature's contributions to people and integrating livestock plays a large role in these crop-livestock systems as they promote recycling of organic materials by using manure for composting or directly as fertilizer and crop residues and by-products as livestock feed. About 15% of the nitrogen applied to crops comes from livestock manure, highlighting synergies resulting from crop-livestock integration. Mixed farming allows alternating cropping-pasture rotational cycles that promote a regenerative soil fertility management.</p>	<p>Alomia-Hinojosa <i>et al.</i> (2019); FAO (2018); G. Martin <i>et al.</i> (2016); B. Paul <i>et al.</i> (2019); Ryschawy <i>et al.</i> (2017); Schut <i>et al.</i> (2021)</p>
Promoting human values and local economies	<p>Community-based agroecological initiatives exemplify the principles of equity and justice and contribute to social resilience. These initiatives involve local communities in decision-making processes, respecting their Indigenous and local knowledge and fostering a sense of ownership over agricultural practices. Community-supported agriculture models, where consumers directly support local farmers, exemplify how agroecology can create relational values and responsibilities between producers and consumers.</p> <p>The <i>Unión Trabajadores de la Tierra</i>, started in Argentina after the 2001 economic crisis, is an example of food system transformation at scale, counting 22,334 farming families out of the 33,400 small family farms in the country, that produce agroecological food at affordable prices through 420 selling points and online sales, independent from government support</p>	<p>Future of Food (2024); Hvitsand (2016); Timmermann (2020); Tittonell <i>et al.</i> (2020); van den Berg <i>et al.</i> (2022)</p>

and action (Chapter 1). Progress and performance of agroecological transitions are evaluated through metrics that represent ten principles: diversity, efficiency, recycling, resilience, synergies, human and social values, knowledge co-creation and sharing, culture and food traditions, circular and solidarity economy and responsible governance (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019). Agroecological transitions challenge established views, structures and practices and have four main characteristics:

- Diverse entry points: Agroecological transitions can start from changing views, including the way farmers, consumers, policy makers and companies see nature, its contributions, as well as the consequences of their production, trading and consumption practices and their hidden costs, and adopt a regenerative mindset² (Gosnell, 2022) (Strategy 5). Changing structures can result in agroecological transitions through new policy frameworks (such as the goal of reaching 25% organic farming by 2030 in the European Union) and governance systems (securing Indigenous Peoples' self-determination right), as was the case for the *Reservas Campesinas* in Colombia (see Strategy 4) (Acevedo Osorio & Chohan, 2019). Transitions can also start by altering practices, steered by financial tools such as subsidies or taxes, by new regulations or through

re-educating key food system actors (Strategies 2, 3 and 5).

- Context-specific approaches: Recognizing diverse contexts is crucial, as solutions must be adapted to ecological and cultural nuances. Agroecological knowledge is co-constructed with farmers, through organizing co-innovation platforms and multi-actor learning centres (Dogliotti *et al.*, 2014; Ruggia *et al.*, 2021, 2021; Tittonell *et al.*, 2021) and integrated with both formal and informal markets (Strategy 3). The deployment of co-innovation platforms to support agroecological transitions is not restricted to smallholder farming, as illustrated by the growing number of large-scale farmers moving to context-specific agroecological, regenerative practices (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2016).
- Iterative learning: Agroecology advocates for ongoing monitoring, evaluation and learning, fostering resilience and continuous improvement (Tittonell, 2020). Agroecological transitions operate through cycles of design-evaluation-redesign-re-evaluation that allow reflexive learning and adaptive management towards transformation. This form of iterative learning, in which innovations that fit local contexts are expected to

emerge, tends to collide with classic approaches to programme planning through rigid theories of change (**Annex 5.7.2**). Co-innovation platforms are ideal settings for iterative learning among different actors of the food system (Ruggia *et al.*, 2021).

- **System-wide reorganization:** Parallel and simultaneous shifts in production practices and consumption patterns, although slow and gradual, are important entry points for change in the technological and economic domains. An example of this is the current gradual shift towards plant-based food replacing meat and dairy in some parts of the world, which is opening opportunities for new farming business models, technologies, products and markets. However, many markets impose multiple barriers to farmers in transition to agroecology. Farm diversification often involves growing crops or raising animals that are less in demand on the market compared to dominant species, such as maize, wheat, chickens, cows or soya. Landscape aesthetics, technological and 'cultural' barriers may prevent farmers from adopting disruptive farming

systems such as agroforestry, especially in large-scale mechanized agriculture. Policy barriers include subsidy systems directed to monocrops or other species mixes defined legally as 'crops'. Addressing such system-wide barriers (**Strategies 1, 2, 3 and 4**) is a prerequisite for broad agroecological transitions that can support biodiversity restoration.

Through real world examples, agroecological transitions illustrate different theoretical approaches to transformative change, as described in **Chapter 3**. The latest advances in science and technology are in dialogue with Indigenous and local knowledge through co-creation approaches, implemented through co-innovation platforms. The systemic nature of agroecological transitions described above are often driven by inner transformations, including the values, beliefs and worldviews of key actors in the food system, especially of the farmers and consumers (Gosnell, 2022; Gosnell *et al.*, 2019). However, agroecological transitions depend on social and political activism to empower marginalized groups (e.g., smallholder or landless farmers) to transform power relations² and provoke

Figure 5.16 **Transition pathways from natural to traditional and industrial farming systems.**

Multiple possible states of nature illustrating the transition pathways from natural to traditional and industrial farming systems (black dashed line) and from these and degraded states to agroecological farming systems (grey arrows) through combinations of regenerative elements, ecological intensification² and diversification. Agroecology integrates high management intensity and productivity with the provision of multiple ecosystem services through the design of diverse and multifunctional farming systems and landscapes (a combination of transition frameworks proposed by Griffon (2009) and Tittone (2020)).

structural changes in economic, cultural, political and social spheres.

Agroecology is not just another production technique but an approach to holistic food system transformation, towards democratisation of food and sovereignty. Agroecology as science, practice and movement operates in the different phases of transformative change as represented by **Figure 3.9 in Chapter 3**: i) unlearning current practices and destabilizing existing regimes (**Strategies 1, 2 and 3**), ii) creating new governance (**Strategy 4**) and iii) nurturing niches (**Strategy 1 and 5**). The political dimension of agroecology (Molina *et al.*, 2019), questioning existing structures and power imbalances, is crucial to unlock regimes towards transformative change, but also to create conducive conditions for expanding and embedding change through upscaling² and institutionalization (i.e., the right side of **Figure 3.9 in Chapter 3**). This is illustrated by the case of the *Unión Trabajadores de la Tierra* in Argentina

(**Table 5.5**). Alternative metrics are needed to assess agroecological performance (**Strategy 3**).

Agroecological transitions involve transformative reconfigurations of current food systems and examples from countries and regions where they are taking place illustrate the synergistic effects of the five strategies for transformative change proposed here. Transitions take place simultaneously through views (including values, attitudes and worldviews), structures (such as reconfigurations in governance and institutions) and practices (for example, sectorial actions to shift current food production practices and natural resource management) (Tittonnell, 2020).

Figure 5.17 illustrates how these shifts correspond to the five strategies aimed at reversing the effect of direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. (See **Table 5.5** for contributions of agroecological transitions to achieving specific actions within these strategies).

5.9 CONCLUSION

Drawing on a comprehensive assessment of different sources of knowledge, **Chapter 5** identified five main strategies, each with multiple actions and instruments that have the potential to facilitate, catalyse and/or support transformative change by addressing the direct and indirect drivers and underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. The strategies range from conserving remaining biodiversity and regenerating places that have been degraded, to dismantling or reforming powerful institutions and structures responsible for maintaining the status quo, to shifting societal values and norms to better recognize and support human-nature interdependencies. The scope and scale of transformative change needed is enormous and for many, overwhelming, but as **Chapter 5** illustrates, a diverse set of concrete actions can be woven together by a variety of different actors into strategic and integrative pathways leading towards the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity, where humans and nature live in harmony.

This chapter shows that there is no single instrument or universal "to-do-list" for transformative change. Rather, deliberate transformative change for a just and sustainable world, as opposed to transformative change occurring unintentionally as a byproduct of other processes, is an iterative and highly contested, collective process involving ever-increasing numbers of actors making efforts to shift existing views, structures and practices based on transformative principles through a diversity of strategies and actions that both address persistent challenges that suppress solutions and introduce new pathways.

There are important methodological and data gaps in assessing the effectiveness and the potential social impacts of strategies, actions and instruments with transformative potential, as well as an insufficient understanding of the roles played by different actors and actor coalitions in it (**Box 5.3**). Knowledge gaps range from the lack of instruments for analysing values beyond a utilitarian focus to exploring the potential of the plurality of alternative ways of relating to nature. As pathways to transformative change combine actions from different strategies, transdisciplinary studies that engage actors involved in or affected by deliberate transformation are needed to analyse accumulated effects and trade-offs in different dimensions, as well as the complementarities and/or synergistic effects for nature and people. Knowledge gaps also include a lack of understanding of power structures and vested interests on various levels. There is also a need to further develop scenarios and plural pathways of how to enable transformative change across multiple levels from local to global.

No single strategy, specific list of actions or unique pathway brings about transformative change in all contexts. No single actor, or actor coalition, brings about transformative

change. Rather, there are diverse and complex processes that can be mobilized or activated by multiple actors, organizations, institutions and movements, acting alone or in coalition, at local to regional to global scales, to engage in actions to realize transformative potential for a just and sustainable world. The context-specific implementation of a mosaic and combinations of actions by multiple actors results in nonlinear trajectories of change. The strategic planning of transformative change is better achieved with experimentation, monitoring and reflexive evaluation that leads to adaptive learning and action to adjust to remain on track towards realizing desired visions. The strategies and pathways outlined in this chapter are not per se transformative, but rather entry points to transformative processes, as the effectiveness of actions will always be context and time-dependent and will benefit from transdisciplinary methodologies to continuously learn and reflect on pathways towards a sustainable future.

Transformative processes face challenges (**Chapter 4**) which, if they are to be overcome, can be accelerated with deeper evaluation and adjustments of the views, structures and practices that determine how human-nature relationships evolve. Revising these three dimensions in alignment with the principles of transformative change for a just and sustainable world (**Chapter 1**) and driven by visions of a just and sustainable world (**Chapter 2**) can create possibilities for addressing these challenges and thereby influencing actors' willingness to engage in deliberate transformative change. Including and integrating new perspectives and approaches to transformative change (**Chapter 3**) can lead to alternative and potentially complementary pathways that can change the ways actors operate and respond to sustainability challenges.

Scaling transformative change is a process of generating new and more coherent patterns across views, structures and practices in ways that are contextual and aligned with principles of equity and justice, pluralism and inclusion, respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships and adaptive learning and action, regardless of the level of intervention. It involves thinking, organizing and doing things differently on all levels to address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. In a globalizing and interconnected world, overcoming challenges to transformative change can be accelerated by engaging coalitions of actors and actor groups to negotiate and manage trade-offs and unintended consequences, which involves engaging with those resisting or opposing change. Transformative change is about designing and implementing strategies and actions that contribute to visions for global sustainability, while also showcasing opportunities for transformative change through the many initiatives taking place around the world. Most of all, transformative change involves a willingness and courage to show up differently and to act on behalf of a just and sustainable world.

Box 5.3 Knowledge gaps related to material covered in Chapter 5.

The assessment of literature related to strategies and actions that could bring about transformative change for people and nature, highlights various interconnected knowledge gaps. These relate to how to articulate strategies, actions and instruments in the solution space, but also to data gaps for observation and monitoring, understanding of inner transformation² and pathway or projection. There is a dearth of knowledge on what actions simultaneously work for nature and people, how they interact and jointly reverse trends of nature's decline and social issues, under what social-ecological contexts and factor constellations and across which timescale. Overall, there is a need for research projects that cover all these dimensions of transformative action to provide better scientific background on deliberate transformative change. Specific knowledge gaps are listed below according to the five strategies that structure **Chapter 5** and its pathways section.

Strategy 1: Conserve and regenerate places of value to nature and people

- Assessment of social movements to protect nature: While there is information on the actions taken by social movements against threats to the environment, there is no estimation of the effectiveness of such actions (e.g., area safeguarded through the action of social movements or species protected).
- Assessment of nature rights implementation: An analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches to implementing Rights of Nature, prohibiting ecocide, focusing on their effectiveness in protecting nature, is lacking.
- Evaluation of environmental and social safeguards: Another knowledge gap refers to the identification of challenges to effective implementation and enforcement of environmental and social impact assessments, along with existing land use policies.

Strategy 2: Drive systemic change in the sectors most responsible for nature's decline

- Application of National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans: Information is lacking on how countries specifically integrate nature into sectoral policy plans, focusing on translating nature mainstreaming into action plans.
- Nature reliance assessment: At the national level, few countries have assessed their dependence on nature. Information on the economic contributions of nature will be essential to inform policy decisions.
- Private sector accountability: Increased public reporting of the private sector would allow the analysis of the environmental impact of companies and monitor progress with contributions of business and financial institutions to nature targets at various scales. This can be promoted by developing necessary tools and methods for the private sector to increase its accountability.

- Subsidies to economic sectors responsible for biodiversity loss and nature decline evaluation: More information is needed examining the environmental impact of subsidies on economic activities, in particular metal extraction and processing. Information is needed both regarding monetary cost and environmental and health impacts.
- The extent and impact of corruption: Data, or even estimates, of the impact of corruption in public and private operations and how particular powerful lobbying groups exert pressure to maintain economic activities that are harmful to nature is completely absent from the literature.

Strategy 3: Transform economic systems for nature and equity

- Methodology to assess non-monetary values: There is a need for methodologies to assess the non-monetary benefits of practices proposed as transformative. For instance, what are the benefits for people and nature of practices such as agroecology or regenerative agriculture?² What is the net impact of agroecological farming on GHG emissions and ecological indicators? How does it compare to other agricultural production options?
- Assessment of benefits and trade-offs of different transformative actions: Comparing benefits and trade-offs of different transformative actions across various ecosystems and the contexts would be useful to guide policy choices.
- Incorporating biodiversity into growth measures: There is a lack of consistency on how to incorporate nature's contributions to people into emergent growth measures such as inclusive wealth index, especially in developing countries.
- Power in economic and financial systems at different scales: There is a need to better understand how power imbalances and different types of inequalities affect directly and indirect nature decline and equity. Further understanding the complex feedback loops that link direct and indirectly drivers of nature decline to different dimensions of inequality is also essential to be able to identify the best context-specific actions for transformative change that address nature decline and equity. There is a need for more clearly identified and strategically integrated actions to overcome power structures that maintain path-dependencies that negatively affect nature and equity (e.g., through corruption, elite capture and lobbying, market power or financial dependence).

Strategy 4: Transform governance systems to be inclusive, accountable and adaptive

- Comparative evaluation framework: There is a need to develop consistent evaluation measures to assess the effectiveness of measures with transformative potential,

Box 5 3

such as governance instruments as well as their impacts on nature and sustainability.

- Insights on underlying institutional configurations that enable integrated policies: Analysis of institutional settings and power structures are needed to understand barriers to integration of biodiversity into sector policies and governance processes.
- Understanding complementary functions in polycentric networks and tele-coupling governance: There is a gap in the understanding of polycentric governance and tele-coupling in global value chains, focusing on the role of actors, power dynamics and potential for transformative change.
- Accountability and reflexive governance in multi-level, multi-actor settings: There are gaps in knowledge associated with adaptive learning processes and administrative entrepreneurship in complex governance structures to address sustainability challenges effectively, with a specific focus on biodiversity governance.

Strategy 5: Shifting societal views and values to recognize and prioritize the fundamental interconnections between humans and nature.

- Exploring inner transformation: There are gaps in knowledge about tools for inner transformation (also known as inner-outer transformation, existential resilience, or existential sustainability) through culturally sensitive and inclusive practices, education, psycho-social practices, facilitation processes, contemplative, psychological and cognitive-behavioural approaches.
- Methodologies for inclusive collective action: There are gaps in knowledge about the methods to reconcile diverse perspectives with the need for unified collective action, overcoming dominant narratives and fostering inclusive spaces for envisioning new possibilities.
- Actions to phase out views that contribute to nature decline: Analysis of actions are needed to enhance regenerative perspectives that promote sustainable interactions with the natural world while diminishing views to contribute to biodiversity degradation.
- Role of Indigenous worldviews: Gaps exist in the understanding of Indigenous worldviews, which often emphasize interconnectedness with nature

and can enhance biodiversity conservation and land management practices.

- Guided transformative learning: There is a need to develop methods to facilitate transformative learning in sectors contributing to nature's decline, aiming to shift values and worldviews towards sustainability.
- Strategies for cultural transformation: Analyses are needed to understand the role of arts, humanities, social movements, unitive visions, narratives and religion in promoting sustainable values and worldviews.
- Defining views: A comprehensive definition of 'views' can facilitate monitoring, evaluation and application of measures.
- Analysing consumption patterns: There are gaps in knowledge about the costs of changing consumption patterns and their associated monetary and non-monetary benefits.
- Assessing knowledge co-creation: There are gaps associated to the availability of a greater evidence base to determine if the promise of co-creation is realized in practice and how to institutionalize it. Developing a more robust understanding of effective co-creation practices, the circumstances in which they work and creating heuristics² to guide practitioners would be useful.

Pathways

- Transformation pathways that take diverse worldviews: There are gaps in knowledge about pathways to bring about transformative change which take diverse worldviews into account, including Indigenous and local knowledge.
- Better scenarios and plural pathways: Global scenarios do not fully address transformative change for improving nature, nature's contributions to people and good quality of life. There is a need to further develop scenarios and plural pathways to enable transformative change across multiple levels from local to global.
- Guidance on how to co-design and implement transformative pathways: Scientific contributions such as this assessment provide insights on transformation. There is a need for transdisciplinary processes to apply, test and improve projects that cover the multi-actor and multi-scalar complexity of transformative change.

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